

Guidelines of circular economy models for each Living Lab

Deliverable 4.3

D4.3 Guidelines of circular economy models for each Living Lab

Review of existing circular economy models based on the indicators and list of circular opportunities adapted to a water-smart society in the B-WaterSmart context.

Summary

Objectives

The primary objective of Deliverable 4.3 is to define the B-WaterSmart (BWS) methodology to assess circular models in order to identify the potential circular opportunities within each Living Lab (LL) and evaluate their circularity based on selected environmental, social, and economic indicators.

The circular economy (CE) assessment model developed under D4.3 will provide guidance to LLs in monitoring their circularities and assessing the progress of their strategic agendas. Furthermore, the evaluation of existing circular opportunities within LLs will allow them to refine and align the strategic agendas outlined in WP1.

Methodology

For the present deliverable, the WP4 team from BWS has reviewed different sources to analyze the state-of-the-art of circular economy assessment methods, taking the analysis from Deliverable 4.2 “Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs” as reference. After this review, the team has selected the best approach to evaluate the circularity of the different LLs in the BWS context. The deliverable guides the reader through the five steps of the BWS assessment methodology and the efforts made to tailor it to the specific needs of the project. To this aim, the WP4 team has prioritized and simplified the indicators from Deliverable 4.2 reducing the list to 18 indicators to be used for the circularity assessment of LLs. Besides, some of the indicators have been renamed and assessed according to the concepts adopted in the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework (Deliverable D6.3 “Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework” from WP6).

The application of the methodological approach for circularity assessment in each LL first starts with the description of the circularities identified and its involved stakeholders. Thereafter, the assessment itself is conducted by prioritizing one circularity for all the LLs. A list in decreasing order (from most relevant to least) including the main SDGs affecting the prioritized circularity is the last step before measuring the degree of circularity from an indicator-based approach.

The selected indicators for each circularity have been evaluated based on the data gathered by the LL owners and LL mentors according to the specifications from Deliverable 4.1 “Manual of data specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs”. In accordance with that approach, the technical data for the circularity assessment has been divided into different

categories, including water, air, waste, energy, economy and business, green jobs, and social indicators. Moreover, the data collected has considered three scenarios to be analyzed: baseline, circular, and scale-up scenarios.

In the case of social indicators, no scenario design was carried out, as the evaluation was made directly on the perception of the proposed solutions. Most of the qualitative information on social indicators is based on the content of Deliverable 5.4 “Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviors towards water-smart solutions” (WP5) as well as observation at CoP meetings and focus groups. For the case of governance-related aspects, self-assessment of the OECD principles carried out in “D5.5. Drivers and barriers: proposal for a new governance model” (WP5) was taken into account.

Results

The main results of the present deliverable D4.3 “Guidelines of circular economy models for each Living Lab” are the identification, monitoring and assessment of the different circular opportunities from all the LLs.

Specifically, the results of this deliverable are:

- A review of existing circular economy assessment methodologies.
- A comprehensive assessment methodology to guide LLs in identifying and monitoring their circularities and its circular business models.
- The evaluation of indicators related to circularity to support LLs in the process of refining and aligning the strategic agendas.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AC	Activated Carbon
AD	Anaerobic Digestion
AdTA	Águas do Tejo Atlântico
AMAEM	Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante, Empresa Mixta
ANBI	Unione Regionale Consorzi Gestione e Tutela del Territorio e Acque Irrigue
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
ARERA	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente
ARH	Administração da Região Hidrográfica
ARPAV	Agenzia Regionale per la Prevenzione e Protezione Ambientale del Veneto
ARS LVT	Administração Regional de Saúde de Lisboa e Vale do Tejo
B2EU	B2 European Union Consulting
BM_c, CBM	Circular Business Model
BM_{CE}	Circular Economy Business Model in practice
BM_{tot}	Total Business Models
BWS	B-WaterSmart
C	Circularity
Ca²⁺	Calcium
CCA	Circular Consumption Assessment
CE	Circular Economy
CEA	Circular Efficiency Assessment
CEPA	Circular Economy Performance Assessment
CFP	Carbon Footprint
CFP_{co-digestion}	Carbon Footprint in Co-digestion
CGRI	Circularity Gap Reporting Initiative
Cl⁻	Chlorine

CML	Câmara Municipal de Lisboa
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
CoP	Community on Practice
COTEC	Council of Occupational Therapists for European Countries
CPA	Circular Product Assessment
D	Deliverable
DMK	Deutsches Milchkontor
DWTP	Drinking Water Treatment Plant
EASAC	European Academies' Science Advisory Council
EC	Electrochlorination
E_{co-digestion}	Energy Consumption in co-digestion
E_{eff}	Energy Consumption
E_{eff,co-digestion}	Energy Consumption in co-digestion
EF	East Frisia
ENEL	Ente Nazionale per l'Energia Elettrica
EP	Energy Production
EPAL	Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres
EPSAR	Entidad Pública de Saneamiento de Aguas Residuales
eq	Equivalent
E_{re}	Energy produced
ERSAR	Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos
EU	European Union
EURES	European Union Resources Efficiency Scoreboard
Eurostat	European Statistical Office
E_w	Energy consumed from a treatment
FG	Focus Group
FPA	Fertilizer Production Avoided

GJ	Green Job
kWh	Kilowatt hour
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LL	Living Lab
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil
L_{net}	Length of the network
LWL	Linear Water Losses
m	Meters
Mg²⁺	Magnesium
Na⁺	Sodium
NaClO	Sodium hypochlorite
NGJ	Number of Green Jobs
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NJ	Number of Jobs
npU	Non-potable Uses
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
OOWV	Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband
p.e.	Population equivalent
PIF	Fusina Integrated Project
PSKW	Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt
R&DI	Research, Development and Innovation
RO	Reverse Osmosis
RRR	Resource Recovery Revenues
RW	Reclaimed Water
RWnpU	Reclaimed Water for non-potable Uses
RWP	Reclaimed Water Production
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals

SED	Selective Electrodialysis
SRL	Societal Readiness Levels
T	Task
THP	Thermal Hydrolysis Process
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWW	Treated Wastewater
UASB	Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket
UF	Ultrafiltration
UV	Ultraviolet
VLAKWA	Vlaams Kenniscentrum Water
V_{loss}	Annual water losses
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WFN	Water Footprint Network
WFP	Water Footprint
WFP_{dw}	Water Footprint in the Drinking Water system
WFP_{ww}	Water Footprint in the Wastewater system
WICER	Water in Circular Economy and Resilience
W_{i,in}	Total potential recoverable material entering the treatment process or activity
W_{i,re}	Material recovered
WP	Work Package
WR	Water related-materials' Recovery
WSC	Water Storage Capacity
W_{treated}	Water treated
WW	Wastewater
WWT_{eff}	Effective Wastewater Treatment
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

Revision history

Feedback received September 2024	How the feedback has been integrated in D4.3
<p>The executive summary shall be reviewed as it rather stands as an introduction. The report lacks a clear executive summary that outlines the key conclusions about the circular economy frameworks that have been designed to date, and key results derived from the assessment of the indicators in the LLs.</p>	<p>The executive summary has been changed and adapted according to the reviewer request (page 15).</p>
<p>The introduction should highlight how this report serves the purpose of Task 4.2, i.e., “we will provide a list of CE opportunities for each LL to be further evaluated (D 4.3) (...)”.</p>	<p>A short paragraph highlighting the purpose of this report has been added at the start of the section “1. Introduction” (page 16).</p>
<p>The report should also outline what e.g., the 10 guidelines are for assessing circular economy models, would other cities want to replicate the methodology. A section should be added.</p>	<p>This information has been included in section 2.2.1 (pages 24-25). Also this has been highlighted in the executive summary section.</p>
<p>A paragraph should be added in “data collection”. It shall indicate whether the collected data were quantitatively and qualitatively adequate to underpin the indicators. This aspect is very important to assess the relevance and reliability of the indicators (e.g., Alicante, Venice, Bodø).</p>	<p>The section has been complemented with more information and an additional paragraph has been added in section 2.2.1, “4) Data collection” (page 28).</p>
<p>A brief introduction should be added to each LL to provide the key results arising from the circularity assessment (e.g., in a box).</p>	<p>A text box has been added in section “3.3 Circularity assessment” for each LL highlighting the key results: LL Alicante (page 45), LL Lisbon (page 57), LL Venice (page 70), LL East Frisia (page 84), LL Flanders (page 94), LL Bodø (page 104).</p>
<p>As the report is for public consultation, it should be reviewed to make it more reader-friendly, by e.g., including subtitles in the long sections.</p>	<p>Subtitles have been added in long sections (i.e. in section “1. Introduction”).</p>
<p>Will the deliverable be published once all the data are collected and analysed to produce the indicators (e.g. Venice, Flanders)?</p>	<p>The decision to update data periodically and redo the circularity assessment and publish final results, will be at the discretion of each LL. Some LLs, like Venice, are already in the process of preparing a scientific publication in collaboration with other partners, such as SINTEF, to disseminate their findings. In addition to potential publications, LLs have the</p>

	<p>option to make their datasets and assessment results through open access repositories like Zenodo. According to the project's data management plan, datasets can be published in public repositories once the LL has consensus from stakeholders. The timing and scope of this will depend on the agreements reached by the respective LLs. For example, Venice is already working on a way to make datasets publicly available to allow other researchers and projects to access and benefit from this data.</p>
<p>Typo to be corrected page 52.</p>	<p>Typos have been corrected (now page 54).</p>
<p>Feedback received - February 2025</p>	
<p>All the comments were addressed - nonetheless the brief introduction to each LL to provide the key results arising from the circularity assessment is very general and does not provide much information.</p> <p>Please make a concrete summary (preferably) by bullet points. Thank you</p>	<p>The summaries for each LL have been improved accordingly at the beginning of sections 3.3.1 to 3.3.6 (pages 45 Alicante, 58 Lisbon, 71 Venice, 86 East Frisia, 96 Flanders and 106 Bodo).</p>

Executive summary

The increase in world population and the resulting demand for water, energy and other resources are exerting increasing pressure on soil, water resources and ecosystems. This abrupt surge in demand for natural resources and its subsequent excessive exploitation is adversely affecting water availability, resilience in the energy sector and socio-economic development, among others. Although projections of future water, energy and other resources demands do vary, it is widely agreed that demand in these sectors will significantly increase in the coming decades, while the natural resource base will simultaneously be weakened through climate change and environmental degradation.

The B-WaterSmart project addresses the urgent need for innovative solutions in water-smart management that includes new business models and circular economy (CE) practices across six European coastal cities and regions - named Living Labs (LLs): Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, and Venice. The present deliverable (D4.3) outlines a comprehensive methodology to assess circular opportunities within each LL. The assessment focuses on key environmental, social, and economic indicators tailored to the specific needs of a water-smart society, providing not only strategic guidance to LLs, but also guidelines for its implementation and replication in future projects. These guidelines include a step-by-step approach, starting with context analysis, identifying local CE opportunities and relevant stakeholders, selecting appropriate indicators, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, and conducting periodic monitoring.

After reviewing existing CE models and indicators, 18 key indicators were selected and adapted to monitor circularity in the water-energy-resources nexus addressing aspects such as effective water treatment, energy efficiency, carbon footprint and social acceptance of the water-smart solutions.

This methodology can serve as a replicable model for other cities and regions aiming to implement CE strategies in the water sector.

Key findings include significant improvements in wastewater treatment efficiency, water reuse, and stormwater management, which contributed to reducing energy consumption, carbon footprint and water losses at the same time that enhances freshwater availability.

The assessment demonstrated that adopting CE models in LLs not only enhances resource efficiency and environmental sustainability but also fosters local socio-economic benefits. Each LL has made progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) while advancing their strategic agendas for circularity and water-smartness.

Moreover, the social acceptance of circularities, based on stakeholder engagement across the LLs, confirmed that there is a growing public support for water-smart practices. Governance soundness, another essential factor, was effectively measured and aligned with OECD principles to ensure a robust methodology for decision-making and future adoption of CE initiatives.

In conclusion, this deliverable provides a practical, indicator-based methodology that enables LLs to monitor circularity progress and refine their CE strategies. The lessons learned and results achieved from the assessment will help other regions and cities replicate and adapt this approach to their own context, thus fostering a broader adoption of CE initiatives in the water sector.

1 Introduction

The present deliverable (D4.3) builds on the findings and methodologies carried out during Task 4.2, where a comprehensive list of circular economy (CE) opportunities for each Living Lab (LL) was identified. In D4.3, those opportunities were assessed through a structured indicator-based methodology. This approach intends to evaluate the performance of each LL in achieving its CE strategies embracing the water-energy-resources nexus.

1.1. The importance of circular economy and its monitoring

At a time characterized by mounting environmental challenges and resource constraints, the concept of CE has emerged as a transformative solution with far reaching implications. The current economic paradigm largely follows a linear take-make-dispose model, where resources are extracted to produce goods and services leaving waste as a by-product. Circularity shifts the focus from this linear trajectory to a regenerative approach, in which waste is reintroduced into the productive process as raw materials for new products, creating closed-loop systems. By intertwining sustainability and waste flows reduction, the CE model presents a strategy that is aligned with the objectives of promoting a greener, conscious and feasible Europe.

Introducing circularity within the traditional economy presents a complex challenge that requires a diverse and nuanced approach. Each industry, sector, and even individual product possess unique characteristics and challenges that require tailor-made strategies for incorporating circular practices effectively from the designing phase. Establishing clear procedures to measure alternative circular processes is essential in order to find optimal solutions that can maximize resource efficiency (Smol et al., 2020).

The B-WaterSmart Project aims to establish a benchmark for monitoring and comparing circularities specific to water (and wastewater) activities and its water-energy-resources nexus, providing guidelines for its implementation and replication in future projects.

1.2. Opportunities in the water sector

There are many opportunities in the water sector to integrate circular practices. By introducing water and by-products reuse for urban, agricultural, and industrial uses, communities can increase their resilience to droughts and resource scarcity by reducing their dependence on freshwater sources and raw materials. Meanwhile, there is potential for integrating wastewater treatment with clean energy production, which can serve to power water treatment plants in a self-sustaining manner. As a result, monitoring the effectiveness of innovative circular practices can boost the development and replication of new circularities, turning water treatment into a source of net value to society, rather than a resource sink (Del Borghi et al., 2020; Voulvoulis, 2018).

The importance of water treatment to communities, large and small, makes it an excellent candidate for widespread adoption of CE models. As a key element of public health and environmental protection, water treatment systems are essential but often costly and resource-intensive operations. By transforming these systems from mere resource sinks to generators of net value, we redefine their role within the community. They evolve from being necessary utilities that merely prevent harm to proactive engines of sustainability and resource efficiency.

1.3. Benefits of circular economy models for water management

Within the water-energy-resources nexus, CE models offer a huge range of opportunities and benefits for the region. In the first place, it offers a more efficient and responsible approach to water management. By minimizing freshwater use, improving water treatment processes, and promoting water reuse and resource recovery, these models help to soothe water scarcity and reduce the strain on freshwater resources (Voulvoulis, 2018). Additionally, it encourages the integration of circular water management practices within other sectors, such as energy production and agriculture, fostering a more integrated and sustainable approach to water use (Smol et al., 2020).

This integrated approach to water, energy and resource management contributes significantly to environmental and economic sustainability at the territorial level. From an economic perspective, the adoption of circular practices in water and energy management drives innovation and efficiency in industrial sectors, resulting in reduced operational costs and employment generation. At the local level, Padilla-Rivera et al. (2020) highlight that the interconnection between water, energy and resources not only links industrial sectors, but also brings tangible benefits to society by promoting the CE. This translates into the creation of sustainable public spaces, community participation in environmental projects and more efficient service delivery. Communities that adopt these models experience concrete economic benefits, such as increased local investment and a greater capacity to withstand external economic changes. In addition, the active participation of society strengthens community ties and promotes environmental awareness, leading to more sustainable behaviors at both the individual and collective levels.

Secondly, CE models also address energy challenges (Del Borghi et al., 2020) by promoting energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, and reducing greenhouse gas emissions, thereby contributing to the mitigation of climate change impacts.

Furthermore, CE is committed to the sustainable management of resources. It encourages the adoption of sustainable sourcing practices, the efficient use of raw materials, and the development of innovative technologies to extend the lifespan of products and materials. By closing the resource loop and fostering a circular flow of materials, it minimizes resource depletion, reduces the need for raw materials extraction, and limits environmental degradation associated with resource-intensive industries (Almeida-Guzmán et al., 2020).

Lastly, CE principles play an important role in waste management within the nexus. It emphasizes waste prevention, reduction, recycling, and the recovery of valuable resources from waste streams. By diverting waste from landfill and incineration, it reduces environmental pollution, preserves resources, and creates new local opportunities for the development of those circular activities.

“Circular economy models in the water sector can play a vital role in mitigating climate change impacts by fostering a more sustainable and regenerative economy.”

1.4. Circular business models in the water sector

CE principles emphasize the importance of efficiency within the water-energy-resources nexus, which can be effectively achieved through the implementation of circular business models (CBMs) that focus on sustainable management (Lewandowski, 2016). A CE system requires new business models based on using as few resources for as long as possible, while extracting as much value as possible in the process. CBMs can enable economically viable ways to close loops, i.e. continuously reuse products and materials, using renewable energy when possible (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). However, there is no clear consensus in the literature on what is and is not a CBM.

1.4.1. Definition of circular business models

Based on the literature, a CBM can be defined as a business model comprising five generic strategies: closing (recycling within the system), narrowing (efficiency improvements), extending resource loops (use phase extensions), intensifying resource loops (a more intense use phase), and dematerialising (substitution of products by service and software solutions) (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). In this line, Deliverable 4.1 adopted the definition of a circular business model (CBM) as “the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value with slowing, closing, or narrowing flows of the resource loops” (Oghazi and Mostaghel, 2018, p.3).

1.4.2. Sustainability and circular business models

A CBM can be considered a sustainable business model that offers solutions that create ecological value, protect the environment, empower society, and are economically viable. It deviates from the traditional linear production model by optimizing products along the entire value chain, reducing environmental impact. Scholars and practitioners commonly view CBM as a model with great potential for catalyzing a paradigm shift towards sustainable development, bringing together the business case with the environmental case (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Yet, the relation between sustainability and CBMs requires careful attention and scrutiny.

CBMs, as well as the wider discourse on circularity, have been criticized for under-attending the social pillar of sustainability as the concept focuses heavily on economic rationalities and environmental benefits. The extent to which sustainable principles are incorporated into the design of CBMs and that these result in impact depends on the ambition of decision-makers. Thus, to ensure the move towards a more circular and sustainable mode of operation and to attend to the links between sustainability and the CE concept (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017), it is fundamental to assess CE through indicators that address the different dimensions of sustainability. (Niero and Kalbar, 2019).

For all these reasons, CE monitoring and CBMs offer a holistic and integrated approach that aligns the interests of water, energy, and resources, paving the way for a more sustainable and regenerative economy.

1.5. Monitoring circular economy

Monitoring the circular economy is important for several reasons:

- It allows us to evaluate the progress and effectiveness of circular economy initiatives and activities. By monitoring resource consumption, waste generation and recovery and reuse rates, CE practices can be assessed to determine if the desired targets are achieved.
- It helps us to identify areas where improvement is needed. By analyzing data and trends, specific processes that require attention or intervention can be detected. This enables policymakers, organizations and other stakeholders to develop targeted strategies and interventions to address any bottlenecks or barriers hindering the transition to a CE.
- It provides a basis for benchmarking and comparison. It allows us to assess the performance of different regions, industries, living labs, etc. in adopting circular practices. This comparative analysis can serve as a motivation for stakeholders to improve their circular performance.
- It helps measuring and communicating the environmental, social and economic benefits of circular practices. It enables us to quantify, for example, the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, energy savings, and green job creation.

The monitoring results can be used to inform decision-makers, raise awareness, build support, and mobilize resources for further CE-related activities (Ellen Macarthur Foundation, 2015).

The European Commission and Eurostat have established a framework to monitor progress towards a CE using available statistical data (European Parliament, 2023). This framework, initiated by the European Commission's Circular Economy Action Plan in March 2020, aims to promote sustainable product design, reduce waste, and empower consumers, notably through a "right to repair." Focusing on resource-intensive sectors like electronics, plastics, textiles, and construction, the plan sets ambitious goals for a carbon-neutral, fully circularity by 2050. Subsequent measures were adopted, like several strategies for textiles or EU-wide rules on packaging to reduce waste and encourage bio-based, biodegradable, and compostable materials.

However, the current framework focuses on aspects of the CE related to resource use and waste management, highlighting some projects as clear examples of Europe's dedication to water (European Commission, 2021) by generating reclaimed water in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) for industrial reuse (ULTIMATE), reducing the energy requirements and greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from water treatment processes (NextGen), decentralizing small-scale sewage treatment and effluent reuse in agroforestry (HYDROUSA), water reusing/recycling that distribute the weight of water management over the territory and the users (Project Ô) and recovering nutrients to make fertilizers from domestic wastewater (Run4Life). Moreover, it involves overcoming regulatory barriers to foster symbiotic relationships, facilitating the reuse and exchange of resources between the industry and WWTPs, industrial and urban wastewater treatment systems (Frijns et al., 2021).

According to the World Bank (WICER, 2021), the concept of CE has not been systematically included in high-level discussions related to the water sector, but it offers an opportunity to recognize and capture the full value of water. The Water in Circular Economy and Resilience (WICER) initiative by the World Bank's Global Water Practice aims to help embrace and implement circular and resilience principles in

cities around the world, thereby addressing pressing water challenges and foresting sustainable water management practices, which are essential to ensure the well-being of communities and ecosystems across the globe by improving water security and promoting efficient water use (WICER, 2021). The initiative has developed a framework to guide practitioners who are incorporating the principles in policies and strategies, planning, investment prioritization, and design and operations, ensuring that these practices are tailored to the unique water-related challenges faced by diverse regions, encompassing issues such as water scarcity, pollution prevention, ecosystem conservation, and equitable access to clean and safe water sources, thereby fostering a comprehensive and adaptive approach to sustainable water resource management worldwide.

While the report on the WICER framework offers a comprehensive overview, certain areas need attention. These include the need to encompass a more detailed exploration of specific implementation challenges, emphasizing regional contextualization, incorporating measurable metrics for progress evaluation, providing guidance on effective stakeholder engagement, and offering in-depth case studies for practical insights. Additionally, a deeper examination of WICER's alignment with existing policies, sustained maintenance strategies, and explicit focus on equity and social inclusion would enhance the report's overall guidance for cities and water utilities. Ultimately, the need to adapt CE to the context of water-smartness should be emphasized.

2 Circular economy assessment

2.1 Review of existing circular economy assessment methods

The concept of circularity and its interdependencies between the environment and the economy, began with Pearce and Turner (1990). They defined it as a zero balance between resources consumed and waste release, implementing integrated closed loops that guarantee a continuous recycling and reusing process. However, literature on how to measure circularity started growing in the late 2010s, as increasing evidence on climate change incentivised the development of innovative solutions that can optimize resources and reduce pollution. With standardized metrics in place, businesses, policymakers, and researchers can consistently evaluate the effectiveness of circular approaches, making it easier to identify best practices and share them broadly.

In a context where pressure on natural resources and environmental challenges become increasingly evident, CE indicators emerge as indispensable tools to analyze the effectiveness of economic systems in minimizing waste generation, as well as in promoting the reuse and recycling of materials. In this way, measuring the degree of circularity not only makes it possible to evaluate economic performance from an environmental perspective, but also acts as a strategic guide for governments, companies, and communities on their path towards more sustainable models. For this reason, indicators are decisive for assessing CE progress at different scales, providing a means to measure achievement, reflect changes, and assess performance. Indicators must be relevant, clearly defined, specific, achievable, replicable, universal, time-bound, quantifiable, distinctive, minimal, and useful for improvement areas.

In the Deliverable D4.2 “Definition of circular economy indicators for Living Labs”, a series of categories and subcategories were proposed from a literature review, whose objective was to cover all sectors related to CE.

De Pascale et al., 2021 carried out a systematic review of the literature related to the measurement of circularities. A total of 61 quantitative indicators were surveyed from 137 articles, published from 2000 to 2019 and classified according to their spatial dimensions—macro, micro and meso. The authors provided a dedicated toolkit for the formulation, scaling, and normalization of each indicator. At the micro level, which suits the B-WaterSmart context, Kristensen and Mosgaard (2020) published a detailed review of 30 indicators for measuring circularity. Most of those indicators focused on measuring recycling and end-of-life management, while fewer indicators consider waste-management and resource efficiency. Meanwhile, Rocca et al., 2021 reviewed methods related to Circular Economy Performance Assessment (CEPA), which entail the measurement of the circularity based on life cycle. CEPA comprises three sub-methodologies: Circular Product Assessment (CPA), Circular Consumption Assessment (CCA), and Circular Efficiency Assessment (CEA). Other studies evaluating circularity include qualitative accounts of different approaches and challenges to assess circularity (Lindgreen et al., 2020), and the measurement of circularity through index methods, which involves assessing how well resources are utilized, recycled, and reintegrated into the production process (Elia et al., 2016). These index methods are very important in the context of CE, since they use specific indicators to assess, quantify and create composite measures that reflect the performance of a system in terms of circularity, for example the proportion of materials that are recycled compared to the total generated waste.

On the institutional level, the European Commission launched in 2020 the “New Circular Economy Action Plan for a cleaner and more competitive Europe”. The Plan includes a monitoring framework for capturing key areas of the CE: production and consumption; waste management; secondary raw materials; and competitiveness and innovation (European Commission, 2020). In addition, EUROSTAT put forward a comprehensive set of indicators to monitor progress towards Social Development Goals (SDGs) in the context of the European Union (EUROSTAT, 2023). The list is updated annually and includes relevant measures of circularity that can be applied at the micro level, in a standardized manner to enable comparisons between projects. Meanwhile, the Circular Economy in Cities and Regions report published by the OECD (2020) offers a compendium of CE best practices, obstacles, and opportunities. It also includes an inventory of indicators for measuring circularities at the regional, national, and local level.

Moreover, the studies conducted by Nika et al. (2020, 2022), explore the need to develop a methodology to assess the circularity of wastewater processes, driven by the environmental, economic, and operational challenges faced by the water sector. The studies address greenhouse gas emissions, elevated energy consumption, aging infrastructure, water stress and the underutilization of available data. While harnessing the value of wastewater resources emerges as a viable solution, the absence of a standardized methodology adds complexity to the evaluation.

Furthermore, the studies point out common challenges in existing methodologies, such as the subjective selection of indicators, amalgamation of diverse indicator sets, and the proliferation of indicators leading to inconsistent assessments. In the realm of wastewater process evaluation, the intricate task of adapting technical process indicators to water systems is underscored, where service provision is intricately tied to user behaviors and local climatic conditions.

In response to these challenges, the studies introduce a methodology grounded in principles that place circularity at the epicenter of the assessment process. The outlined steps encompass everything from defining the system to identifying proposed technologies and characterizing resource flows. The significance of circularity indicators is underscored, emphasizing their role in analyzing pivotal areas for sustainable value creation.

The application of this methodology for wastewater treatment, juxtaposed against a conventional prolonged aeration system, showcases the development of a compelling value proposition. The meticulous selection of action indicators reveals tangible enhancements in resource circularity and overall system performance with the new technology. The subsequent sustainability analysis provides quantifiable insights into positive impacts on carbon emissions, economic value, and broader environmental and social outcomes.

In conclusion, the studies underscore the potential for standardizing circularity assessments in wastewater systems, necessitating the classification of resource circularity for more comprehensive and comparable evaluations. The explicit connection between circularity and sustainable value creation, achieved through well-defined value propositions and specific technological actions, is emphasized as a transformative aspect of this research. Although the study focuses on wastewater, it can also be related and applied to the B-WaterSmart context as it considers the water cycle for each of the LLs.

Regarding the social analysis on circularities, the methodology is based on the deliverable 5.4, part of WP5 (Society, Governance, Policy), and contains a preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviors towards water-smart solutions. The social acceptance of technologies in various domains,

such as energy, water, and materials, is crucial for successful integration into society. While existing studies have explored factors influencing acceptance, they often lack a robust conceptual framework. This social acceptance assessment focuses on the type of acceptance, concepts guiding intention/behavior, and the actors involved. Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) and Huijts et al. (2012) provide insights into energy-related acceptance frameworks. Wüstenhagen and colleagues' proposal emphasizes key actors, while Huijts' model delves into psychological factors influencing attitudes and behaviors towards sustainable technologies, applicable beyond energy. Social acceptance studies, mainly on renewable energy, have grown, with a U-curve pattern observed in community acceptance over time (Smith et al., 2018). Upham et al. (2015) present a cross-paradigmatic framework, outlining macro, meso, and micro levels, and different 'actor groups' influencing acceptance.

Water reuse, essential for sustainability, faces barriers in social acceptance. Smith et al. (2018) review literature on water reuse, citing positive community acceptance when considering local needs. Public acceptance studies reveal willingness for recycled water use but highlight reluctance for high-contact applications like drinking or bathing. The social acceptance of innovations like smart meters is crucial for resource efficiency, although data privacy generates public resistance.

Overall, the study of social acceptance in water innovation is evolving, with emerging models like Societal Readiness Levels (SRL) expanding evaluation frameworks. This innovative approach, exemplified by Innovation Fund Denmark's application in the H2020 Project NewHoRRizon, seeks to extend the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to the social sphere. Assessing societal readiness is crucial, especially when expectations for low societal readiness exist. It advocates for realistic transitions toward societal adaptation, involving improved information dissemination and direct stakeholder involvement. B-WaterSmart's interdisciplinary model, proposed and discussed in the Milestone 7 (Gomes et al., 2021), integrates concepts from environmental sociology and psychology, emphasizing psychosocial factors influencing acceptance. It identifies dimensions like risk perception, fairness, trust, and personal norms. The B-WaterSmart project employs a comprehensive model to analyze social acceptance of water-smart solutions, considering psychosocial factors, contextual/individual elements, and different levels of acceptance. The model serves as a framework for understanding and addressing key acceptance issues within the project.

With regards to the governance analysis on circularities, the report on Deliverable 5.5 provides a snapshot of current challenges in water governance across the 6 Living Labs of B-WaterSmart. It aligns with the 12 OECD Principles for Water Governance (2015), emphasizing Effectiveness, Efficiency, Trust, and Engagement, in line with SDG 6 (OECD, 2015).

Since 2015, the OECD Water Governance Initiative has developed an indicator framework and compiled 50+ best practices to enhance water governance. The 'Turning the Tide' report (March 2023) underscores the global perspective needed for water management, as reflected in the UN's Water Action Agenda (GA resolution 75/212) (OECD, 2022).

Furthermore, B-WaterSmart addresses challenges in line with EU policies like the Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan, aiming to be climate-resilient by 2050. Governance must align with SDGs, requiring a balanced, bottom-up and top-down approach, as seen in the detailed assessment of B-WaterSmart Living Labs (Gurría, 2019). Circular Economy (CE) is proposed for sustainable water management, involving new technologies and business models. Despite technological advances,

sociotechnical barriers persist, demanding stronger policy coherence and institutional support. Circular water schemes often transcend regulatory boundaries, necessitating an efficient governance structure (Frijns et al., 2016).

Addressing circularity and governance challenges requires a multi-dimensional approach. B-WaterSmart's Living Labs, anchored in co-creation and Communities of Practice, involve stakeholders for innovative solutions. Trust-building includes transparent data provision. Effective use of technology is crucial for monitoring, evaluation, and communication, ensuring criteria of effectiveness, efficiency, equity, and sustainability (Villa-Landa Sokolova & Perero Van Hove, 2022).

2.2 An indicator-based approach to assess circular economy

Using indicators for CE assessment is crucial for economic assessment at all scales, from the micro (businesses) level to the macro (regional and national) to global. There are several studies that review and present assessment tools for CE projects and initiatives based on indicators, as mentioned above.

The European Commission has developed a monitoring framework to measure the progress of the CE in all stages of the life cycle of resources, products, and services (OECD, 2020). The framework includes a wide variety of suggested indicators and an overview of relevant indicators to measure progress in the circular transition. The Netherlands' monitoring system for the CE is also inspired by EC proposals for monitoring the CE and includes a wide variety of suggested indicators and an overview of relevant indicators to measure progress in the circular transition.

One example is a study that is about a comprehensive multi-level CE assessment framework that provides a set of indicators and metrics with sector-specific dimensions (Ahmed et al., 2022).

The lack of a systemic approach of the circular economy indicators is still a challenge. To move towards a system change, it is necessary for indicators to measure and control several factors (Butković, 2021). A comprehensive and standardized set of indicators is crucial for the comprehensiveness and objectivity of circular economy assessment methods. The development of a common framework and standardized indicators can help to identify areas for improvement, measure progress towards a circular economy, and inform decision-makers. By using these assessment methods, we can promote environmental sustainability, reduce waste, and create economic value through the reuse and recycling of materials and products.

2.2.1 Description of the circular assessment methodology

The approach used to evaluate the circularity of the different LLs is derived from the methodology discussed in the previous chapter, with a special emphasis on maximizing its effectiveness and impacts in the LLs. Additionally, efforts have been made to standardize existing indicators and tailor them to the specific needs of the B-WaterSmart project.

The guidelines or method for the circular assessment provided in this deliverable can also be replicated beyond the scope of the B-WaterSmart project, to grow and expand CE strategies in other cities and regions. These guidelines include: context analysis, identifying local CE opportunities and its associated stakeholders, selecting appropriate indicators based on environmental, economic, and social factors,

collecting both quantitative and qualitative data, and periodic monitoring, to analyze the results and readapt current strategies.

Figure 1. Methodology of the circularity assessment

The assessment is structured according to the following main steps (Figure 1):

1) **Context analysis**

Definition of the case study and main challenges including LL scope and boundaries.

See also chapter “3.1. LL context and circular economy” for more information on LLs. Extended information on the implementation of the different water-smart technologies and tools of each LL can be also found in D.1.7. “Description and project planning for each Living Lab”, specifically in the section 6 of the deliverable.

2) **Identification of the circularities and stakeholders**

Identify the different circularities and describe them, paying attention to the technical aspect and the different processes involved (scope and boundaries). Specify input and output flows, including their origin, their destination and the procedure or treatment to get from one to the other. It is also necessary to make this identification always around the circularity under study. To this end, and for ease of comprehension, it is recommended to make a process flow chart for each LL and/or circularity.

Identify and map the different stakeholders involved in the LL. Analyze its influence within the LL context and its circularities and understand their roles, expectations and potential collaboration opportunities. Thus, it is recommended to classify the most relevant stakeholders of each LL according to a series of requirements.

First of all, the main aspects of each stakeholder and their relationship with the relevant LLs need to be described. The technical information for each stakeholder was defined, such as the type of entity to which they belong (water industry, engineering company, agricultural company,

research institute, end-user, NGOs, etc.) and their role according to Deliverable D5.1 “Manual of stakeholder mapping and engagement“ description (LL owner, partner, core co-creator, collaborator, follower or observer) (Table 1). On the other hand, the confidentiality status was established according to the interests of the stakeholders, with those that are not confidential appearing and, in the case of confidentiality, they are generalized over the field in which they are involved. Then, it is important to highlight the circularity that each stakeholder is involved in, as well as the sector or category of greatest importance of each one. Once the list of stakeholders has been made, a complete map of the stakeholders of the LL and their classification in ecosystem, industry, agriculture, port and city is included.

Table 1. Role and type of stakeholders in B-WaterSmart CoPs. (Source: Deliverable D5.1)

Role/ profile	Description	Objective for engaging in CoPs	CoP ‘circle’ (D1.1)
Partner	This category applies to the partners involved in BWS Consortium, either as part of a LL or participating/leading the work packages, as well as third parties	Develop BWS products (technologies and tools); build capacity	Core
Core co-creator	Actors and organizations that are core to the development of the BWS solutions, which have a central role and/or influence at the all levels, either in terms of the social acceptance of the solutions (e.g. neighborhood associations) or by directly participating in circular opportunities and BM and the further development of water-smart solutions (e.g. sectoral organizations, agriculture and industry, municipalities, regional/local authorities)	Active participate in the development of BWS innovative solutions/products; raise awareness; improve social acceptance and implementation; build capacity; manager conflicts	Core + Active
Collaborator	Actors and organizations that are core to the development of policies and decision-making related to developing CE in the water sector. This category includes policy decision-makers such as Environmental Agencies and regulators	Overcome policy gaps; support implementation and development of policies and decision-making	Active

Table 1. Role and type of stakeholders in B-WaterSmart CoPs. (Source: Deliverable D5.1) (Continued)

Role/ profile	Description	Objective for engaging in CoPs	CoP 'circle' (D1.1)
Follower	Actors and organizations beyond current geographical scope of BWS LL which will participate in the workshops or dissemination events, to gain a in-depth knowledge of BWS solutions and have the explicit intention of applying them in their respective sectors/areas of intervention (e.g. municipalities, water utilities, companies or sectoral associations in other regions/countries)	Find and develop technical solutions; ensure the replicability, continuity and impact of BWS	Active - Peripheral
Observer	Actors and organizations participating in the workshops or dissemination events who follow the co-creation process but do not actively participate in it (e.g. government institutions, local associations)	Attends meetings, follow co-creation process, and participates in discussion of overarching and general issues	Peripheral

Furthermore, another classification that was taken into account was the group to which they belong according to Task T4.3 “Development of new business models“: internal stakeholders if they are “actors that are responsible for the organization's decisions and activities comprising, for example, shareholders, employees, supervisors, managers, and departments”; value chain stakeholders if they are “actors directly affected by or directly influencing the organization, such as consumers, users, suppliers, retailers, and recycling cooperatives”; and value network stakeholders if they are considered “actors directly or indirectly related with the organization such as government, competitors, inspection agencies and regulatory bodies, society, environment, universities, and local communities”.

Additionally, the category or sector to which each stakeholder belongs, such as water, energy, resources, waste, various, or others, was also specified.

3) **Selection of indicators**

Selection of appropriate indicators from the list considering environmental, governance, economic, social and technological factors. Indicators will model the circularity level related to the water-energy-resources nexus.

The selection of **social indicators** has mainly focused on assessing the involvement, acceptance and understanding of the social environment of each LL towards the proposed circular solutions. However, this analysis has also been accompanied by a study of governance soundness, given its high impact on the implementation of innovative solutions. Therefore, the social indicators are transversal to all LLs, which is why the same indicators have been analyzed and evaluated in all territories.

4) Data collection

In order to carry out the data collection in the most optimal way for the evaluation of the indicators, the same data typology described in deliverable D4.1 “Manual of data specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs” was followed.

Technical data for evaluating CE opportunities in LLs was divided into categories, including water-related data (balances, drinking water and process water consumption, water quality, wastewater flows), energy consumption and production, waste and emission types, materials inputs and products outflows, reclaimed water production, and more, like carbon and water footprints.

Data considered for the assessment was both qualitative and quantitative to capture a comprehensive understanding of the LL context. A detailed protocol is developed specifying the data collection methods, frequency and types of information needed, according to the demand of each LL. Data collected considered different scenarios to be analyzed.

The scenarios considered were at least:

- **Baseline scenario:** data values should be from the baseline period of time (before the project/circularity implementation).
- **Circular scenario:** data values should be from the circular scenario period of time (with the circularity implemented). The scenario considers the implementations and pilots during the project.
- **Scale-up scenario:** data values should be from the scaled-up scenario (beyond the scope of the B-Water project). This scenario considers all the potential circularities that could be considered in a future, as well as the scale-up (full scale, replication) of the solutions.

An analysis and validation of the data received also was done in order to adequately address the different indicators, ensuring their relevance, representativity and reliability. Quantitative data, such as water-related data, energy consumption and production, waste and emission types, etc. provided measurable and comparable insights across the different scenarios analyzed. Strict data collection protocols were followed to capture real-time measurements (e.g. from sensor-based monitoring systems with periodic reporting from LL operators). To ensure representativeness of quantitative data, average values were calculated based on data sampled across different time periods and operational conditions, minimizing biases and ensuring that the results reflect the full scope of each LL circularity.

Qualitative data, derived from stakeholder engagement activities, focus groups, interviews, etc. was used for the social indicators.

It is important to note that in the case of social indicators, no scenario design was carried out, as the evaluation is made directly on the perception of the proposed solutions. Also, given the cross-cutting nature of the collaborative activities, it was not possible to analyze the social indicators for each of the circularities. Instead, the various innovative solutions addressed in the different collaborative actions were evaluated for each LL.

To this end, socio-economic data was required, integrating economic, governance, social and environmental perspectives. This layer covers customer segments, value proposition, channels, customer relationships, revenue stream, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, etc. Socio-economic data pretended to cover business performance, financing and investment, but also employment, governance and social perception towards circularities.

Most of the qualitative information on social indicators is based on the analysis of stakeholders' attitudes towards the acceptance of water smart solutions carried out in D5.4. "Preliminary report on social acceptance and behaviors towards water-smart solutions" as well as observation at CoP meetings and focus groups. For the case of governance related aspects, self-assessment of the OECD principles carried out in D5.5. "Drivers and barriers: proposal for a new governance model" was taken into account.

In summary, the comprehensive list of the data sources is shown below:

- Template with Operational data from the LLs (see Appendix B - MS21)
- Surveys
- Interviews
- Communities of Practice (CoPs)
- Evaluation questionnaires carried out in each collaborative/informative session
- Focus groups
- Literature review
- Policy frameworks, territorial strategic agendas and action plans (i.e. the Green Deal, the Action Plan for Circular Economy, the EU Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change and the new Drinking Water Directive)
- Other information from the project (Deliverables, Milestones, WPs, etc.)

5) Assessment

Once the circularities and stakeholders have been defined, the assessment itself is carried out, prioritizing circularity number 1 of all the LLs. Next, the main SDGs affecting circularity are detailed in decreasing order (from most important to least important). The prioritization of the SDGs can be done through a survey to a collective of people and experts involved in the LL ecosystem. To assess the **water, air, waste, energy, economy and business and green jobs** indicators, a series of equations were applied to quantify them (see section 2.3 and Appendix A from the present deliverable for more information).

To assess the level of **social acceptance**, the contents of deliverable D5.4, titled "Preliminary Report on Social Acceptance and Behaviors Towards Water-Smart Solutions," have been reviewed. That report aims to gather exploratory data for assessing social acceptance issues in the different LLs. The report delves into risk perceptions, trust, justice, attitudes, and other issues influencing circular solutions' adoption. In this sense, discussions with stakeholders through interviews, focus groups, and CoP meetings helped identify key issues related to the acceptance. For this analysis, the information in the document D5.4 has been analyzed, distinguishing between the most favorable and unfavorable points to provide a balanced perspective. The positions have been summarized into phrases, subsequently categorized in a table. On the one hand, in the presence of a socially aware and committed community to implement circular solutions, the value "**supportive**" has been assigned. On the other hand,

when the community has demonstrated resistance to change or lacked awareness, the value “**resistant**” has been assigned. Finally, in the presence of a balance between favorable and unfavorable stances, the value “**neutral**” has been chosen.

Stakeholder engagement is a complex indicator that encompasses various dimensions. On one hand, the number of participants in workshops is recorded through collected records and minutes. Based on this value, gender distribution is analyzed, considering an activity to be equitable when the presence of both genders is not less than 40% (except for the presence of non-binary individuals). On the other hand, the number of organized activities (focus groups, CoP, etc.) in which diverse stakeholders have participated is also taken into account. Finally, questionnaires have been conducted during participatory activities. Thanks to these questions, 5 levels have been established regarding the degree of stakeholder engagement level: 1. “**Inform**” (1 - 1.5): when there has only been one-way communication, i.e., without active stakeholder participation; 2. “**Consult**” (1.6 - 2.5): when opinions have simply been collected; 3. “**Involve**” (2.6 - 3.5): when there has been mutual learning between organizers and participants; 4. “**Collaborate**” (3.6 - 4.5): when mutual learning is complemented by involvement in decision-making; and 5. “**Empower**” (4.6 - 5): when stakeholders are encouraged to take action.

Also thanks to questionnaires carried out in each collaborative session, the indicator for **awareness and increased understanding** is evaluated. Here again 5 positions are established based on the level of awareness and understanding of the water challenge and the circular solutions: 1. “**Dissociated**” (1 - 1,5), individuals who do not acknowledge the problem and deny it; 2. “**Unaware**” (1,6 - 2,5), people who know about the water related challenges but do not care about them; 3. “**Curious**” (2,6 - 3,5), individuals who understand the problem and are interested in it; 4. “**Aware**” (3,6 - 4,5), those who are also conscious; 5. “**Full understanding**” (4,6 - 5), people who understand the different dimensions of the problem and completely comprehend it.

The D.5.5 “Drivers and Barriers: proposal for a new governance model” provides an overview of key present challenges and recommendations for water governance across the 6 Living Labs of B-WaterSmart. The 12 OECD Principles for Water Governance (2015) were adopted as a framework for the analysis of governance gaps with implications for the selected products and solutions under development in the 6 LLs. The methodology for the assessment is mostly based on the results of the Communities of Practice (CoPs, WP1) and the own diagnosis from LL representatives (owners and mentors). However, in relevant cases, it also includes interviews with key informants (stakeholders and governance experts). The proposed governance assessment uses the results and framework from D.5.5 to determine the **governance soundness** of each LL context. For this purpose, a scoring system is used to quantify the qualitative evaluation of each OECD principle made in D.5.5. By aggregating all scores, an overall score will be produced for each LL context, which will then be normalized to account for differences in data availability and be able to compare each BWS-relevant context. Presented as a percentage, the normalized score will be classified into one of the three categories proposed to determine the governance soundness. Following the OECD principles as the framework for analysis, the assessment will 1. quantify each LL self-assessment developed in D.5.5; 2. present the overall score of each LL in a normalized percentage; 3. classify the normalized score into **stopper, neutral or promoter** according to previously defined thresholds to determine the governance soundness of each LL context.

1. In order to determine the Governance Soundness of the 6 LLs, the **first step is to quantify the governance gaps assessment carried out in D5.5**. For this purpose, the 12 OECD Water Governance Principles are scored in every case according to each Living Lab self-assessment developed in D5.5. A scale from 1 to 3 is used to provide a performance score for each principle, i.e. 1 (poorly performed), 2 (moderately performed) and 3 (well performed). These three indicators are given different colors, red-yellow-green respectively, to make the assessment easier to communicate.

Table 2. Unit of Governance Soundness.

Poorly performed	Moderate performed	Well performed
1	2	3

2. Thereafter, to determine the **Governance Soundness** for each LL, i.e. **stopper, neutral, promoter**, it is proposed to present the aggregate score of each LL at a normalized value in the 0-100 interval, 0 meaning the worst possible result and 100 the best one. Data normalization is used in this context to easily compare the results of each LL governance assessment. The Min-Max method has been selected among all of the available normalization techniques due to its simplicity, efficiency, and widespread use. The total score is normalized to a 0 to 100 scale using the following equation:

$$\text{Normalised Score} = \frac{(\text{Overall result} - \text{Min. Possible Score})}{(\text{Max. Possible Score} - \text{Min. Possible Score})} \times 100$$

Figure 2. Equation used to calculate the Governance Soundness score.

3. The normalized score presented as a percentage is classified into one of the three categories. The thresholds to determine the Governance Soundness of each LL, i.e. **stopper, neutral** and **promoter**, are set with the meaning outlined below:

Table 3. Results of Governance soundness' scale.

Stopper	If the normalized score is less than 35%
Neutral	If the normalized score is equal or between 35% and 70%
Enabler	If the normalized score is more than 70%

6) Results

Finally, the final results of the indicators calculated for each LL are made available and the reasons for their values are discussed, according to the following categories: water, air, waste, energy, economy and business, green jobs and social. All of these help us to have a representation of how the environment can change with the different scenarios and circularities. The results that were quantified for different scenarios were also compared between them for a LL. If data is available, it is also recommended to compare the same indicator for the different LLs.

Also, it is important to highlight the main opportunities of the strategic agenda: implementation of innovative technologies, which can generate a positive environmental impact by improving wastewater treatment efficiency; development of strategic partnerships to collaborate with specialized organizations and companies to boost economic and social impact, promoting job creation and local development; and integration of environmental awareness programmes that can generate positive social impact by engaging the community in sustainable practices.

The results obtained in the **social indicators** are a current and real representation of the social context, as they are based on the sessions carried out during the lifetime of the project. Thus, they should not be extrapolated over time because communities and realities are dynamic and very changeable. Therefore, if this circularity evaluation has continuity, the collaborative sessions must continue at the same time in order to correctly monitor the social indicators overtime.

Moreover, it is important to acknowledge that biases exist in social indicators' results. These biases can arise from various factors, such as the selection of samples, research design, or other cognitive factors affecting individuals. While efforts have been made to minimize bias when evaluating indicators, it is inevitable that some level of bias is present. Thus, in this analysis biases can arise from the evaluators themselves as well as the sample of participants in collaborative sessions. This means that the sample of participants may already have a predisposition towards collaboration in the water sector, which may not be representative of the broader society. Hence, their involvement, perception, and knowledge may not be applicable to the entire population.

Monitoring and quantifying the real impact of implemented circular projects and practices are important aspects to assess effectiveness and long-term sustainability. Establishing a functional monitoring system will allow measuring not only immediate results, but also the impact over time on environmental, economic and social aspects. The collection of accurate and relevant data, together with key performance indicators, will facilitate a comprehensive assessment of project performance. In addition, continuous feedback from all stakeholders, combined with trend analysis and future scenarios, will ensure a better understanding of how circular initiatives positively affect the community, the environment and the economy, thus contributing to a cycle of continuous improvement and strategic adaptation.

2.3 List of circular economy indicators (updated)

Circular economy (CE) indicators are essential for measuring and improving circularity. To make the implementation of circularity in each LL possible, a list of indicators was developed. After the research process and sharing within the project LLs, it was concluded that CE indicators must be relevant, clearly defined, specific, achievable, replicable, universal, time-bounded, distinctive, comparable and useful to be efficient in guiding cities towards the improvement of circularity and water-smartness.

After the prioritization and simplification of the 28 CE indicators that were discussed in Deliverable 4.2 by the WP4 team, it was considered appropriate to reduce the list and readapt the names of some of them, in order to make them more accessible and appropriate for its use in the project context. To this aim, the list from D4.2 has been updated and reduced to **18 indicators** and some of them have been renamed according to the concepts adopted in the Water-Smartness Assessment Framework (Deliverable D6.3 “Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework”) which also received inputs from WP4 and validation from all the members of the LLs. Thus, this adapted list of indicators is detailed in Table 4 below. Also, a more complete list of the indicators with its calculation equations and measurements is described in Appendix A.

Table 4. Final list of circular economy indicators in the water-energy-resources nexus.

Category	Indicator	Unit	Description
Water	1 Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT_{eff})	%	Share of generated wastewater that is treated in wastewater treatment facilities complying with legal requirements.
	2 Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses ($RWnpU$)	%	Volume of reclaimed water used over the total water used for non-potable uses.
	3 Reclaimed Water Production (RWP)	%	Volume of reclaimed water produced (for own use or transfer to third parties) over the volume of treated wastewater or water from other non-conventional sources (e.g. stormwater).
	4 Linear Water Losses (LWL)	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$	Ratio of the volume of yearly water losses and the total length of the supply and/or distribution pipes of the utility for the assessment year.
	5 Water Storage Capacity (WSC)	days	Ratio between the total volume of storage (e.g. tanks for water supply, water storage from non-conventional sources such as rain harvesting systems, reclaimed water storage) and the average flow provided or demanded to the considered system (demands associated to distribution systems, rain harvesting systems, treatment plants, etc.).

Table 4. Final list of circular economy indicators in the water-energy-resources nexus. (Continued)

Category	Indicator	Unit	Description
Water	6 Water Footprint (WFP)	$\text{m}^3 \text{ eq m}^{-3}$ treated water	Water footprint associated with direct and indirect use of water for the consumption of 1 m^3 of drinking water and/or the treatment of 1 m^3 of wastewater. WFP is an indicator of direct and indirect freshwater resources appropriation. Directly used water is the amount used in the production/treatment, while indirect is the amount used in producing products, processes, systems, etc. that is used in the production/treatment of the product. It follows the Water Footprint Network (WFN) methodology.
Air	7 Carbon Footprint (CFP)	$\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ eq m}^{-3}$ treated water	Carbon footprint that is emitted directly and indirectly for the consumption of 1 m^3 of drinking water and/or treatment of 1 m^3 of wastewater.
Waste	8 Water-related materials' Recovery (WR)	%	By-product material or waste that is recovered and is suitable for its reuse after a treatment process or activity to enhance other activities within the site of interest and the organization scope.
	9 Fertilizer Production Avoided (FPA)	%	Nutrient recovered used as a fertilizer in relation to the total nutrient used as fertilizer.
Energy	10 Energy Consumption (E_{eff})	$\text{kWh m}^{-3} // \text{kWh tn}^{-1}$	Ratio of the energy consumption for a treatment process or activity.
	11 Energy Production (EP)	%	Energy produced from a treatment process (e.g. water/wastewater treatment, codigestion) in relation to the total energy consumption.
Economy and business	12 Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR)	%	Potential revenues that are obtained due to by-products recovered from water or wastewater treatment process.
	13 Circular economy business Models in practice (BM_{CE})	%	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-resources nexus that have already been put into practice related to the new and existing models.
Green Jobs	14 Green Jobs (GJ)	%	New jobs created in a circular economy activity over the total amount of jobs.

Social	15 Social Acceptance	Acceptance level (1-3)	Social acceptance refers to the level of approval, recognition, and endorsement that a certain community gives to water-smart solutions, and/or the intentions and likelihood of a community to use and trust in these solutions.
	16 Stakeholder Engagement	Engagement scale (1-5) with gender dimension (balance/imbalance)	Stakeholder engagement is the active participation of local agents and community groups in the decision processes and interventions that affect them (with gender dimension)
	17 Awareness and increased understanding	Awareness scale (1-5)	The process to inform and educate people on water challenges and efficient use of natural resources with the intention of influencing their attitudes.
	18 Governance soundness	Governance soundness (1-3)	The governance soundness of implemented solutions in the LL with the 12 OECD principles of Water Governance based on the key dimensions (Effectiveness, Efficiency, Trust and Engagement).

These indicators will be evaluated from the data gathered from different LLs and their regions, cities, etc. according to the specifications from Task 4.1 and Deliverable 4.1 “Manual of data specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs”.

The main results of the present deliverable D4.3 “Guidelines of circular economy models for each Living Lab” and the evaluation of the indicators will be the assessment, identification and monitoring of the different circular opportunities from all the LLs. Those circular opportunities have also been connected and coordinated with the CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL from WP1 (Deliverable D1.1 “CoP’s architecture and stakeholder mapping for each Living Lab”).

From now and until the end of the project, data will start to be gathered from the LLs periodically to start the identification and monitoring of the circular opportunities and finally get an overview of performance regarding circularity during the next few years. The frequency of evaluation of each indicator will depend on the scope of the LL (industry(ies), municipality, city, region, etc.) and will be adapted for each case also depending on the data availability. It is expected to evaluate the indicators yearly, as a minimum frequency, to get a valuable circularity performance assessment until the end of the project, but also this monitoring could be extended beyond.

Those indicators and the results of the circularity assessment will support the process of refining and aligning the strategic agendas outlined in WP1 for each LL. By delving into the strategic agenda of each LL, specifically addressing key priorities and objectives related to the water-resources-energy nexus, these indicators will help to monitor the objectives of the strategic agendas and its performance status. More information and details on how to evaluate these indicators can be found in Appendix A and in Deliverable 6.3 “Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework”.

Finally, in terms of **social indicators**, firstly, social acceptance is an essential pillar in understanding how affected communities perceive and accept an initiative, determining its long-term success. On the other hand, stakeholder engagement opens a two-way communication channel, allowing local voices to influence decision-making and the way the project is developed.

Moreover, social awareness and understanding is a relevant component, as it fosters understanding and education about the objectives and benefits, not only strengthening the connection between community and initiative, but also laying the foundations for the adoption of sustainable practices at industrial and collective level. Ultimately, the governance soundness underlines the importance of a transparent and effective decision-making structure that inspires trust in the community and fosters the implementation of water smart solutions.

3 Circular economy assessment in the context of B-WaterSmart

3.1 Living Lab context and circular economy

B-WaterSmart has the strategic vision of Living Labs (LLs), whose aim is to promote a transformation towards water-smart economies and society in Europe. This large-scale systemic innovation approach is created to select, connect, and demonstrate a tailor-made set of smart technologies, management, and data solutions to create new business models based on the circular economy and smart water management. In this way, six coastal cities and regions were brought together as LLs with high ambitions to address water-related challenges and opportunities: Alicante (Spain), Lisbon (Portugal), Venice (Italy), East Frisia (Germany), Flanders (Belgium), Bodø (Norway). They were rigorously selected for their complementarity and mutual learning opportunities. LLs can be used as a tool to advance environmental sustainability through economic value, material, and knowledge flows in the CE (Kallai et al., 2020).

LLs emphasize the roles of user involvement, prototyping, testing, and validating in the creation of new technologies, services, products, or systems (Engez et al., 2021). They can help to demonstrate how harmony can be achieved by empowering nature and people in a concrete territorial context, integrating traditional knowledge (Alonso, 2022). Urban LLs are increasingly applied for environmental sustainability and CE, and they aim to regenerate neighborhoods, support CBMs, and foster social innovation (Filho et al., 2022).

The following Table 5 summarizes the main challenges and ambitions of the six LLs and how they address them through CE approaches.

Table 5. Overview of the general context of each Living Lab.

LL	Key challenges	Main ambition	Circular Economy approach
Alicante	Limited water reuse due to high salinity, a lack of local water resources, and the need to reuse 100% of the water regeneration capacity to reduce pressure on agricultural and municipal drinking water use. Also, water scarcity, no local water resources. High conductivity in wastewater, high energy demand for wastewater treatment.	Implementing solutions to transform wastewater treatment plants into biofactories, recovering minerals, nutrients, and energy as well as reclaimed water. Developing a Decision Support System for water reuse and circular economy with stakeholder engagement. Produce reclaimed water per demand (fit for purpose).	Implementation of water-smart solutions for reclaimed water production, brine valorization using selective electro dialysis and electrochlorination, and a low thermal evaporation system for treating rejected water and recovering nutrients. Energy nexus circularities involve co-digestion for biogas production, potentially upgrading to biomethane, and employing a microturbine for energy recovery from water effluents.
Lisbon	Managing growing water demands due to growing population, climate readiness, efficient water allocation, reducing dependence on distant freshwater resources and the need to increase green areas.	Become the first Portuguese city to implement a city-wide network for distributing reclaimed water for reuse in public spaces and specific applications, all to be completed by 2025. Address climate change challenges through green and blue infrastructure solutions.	Decrease in the use of freshwater, improve water use efficiency, promoting water reuse for non-potable uses (irrigation).
Venice	Environmental challenges due to human activities and climate change, especially because of the big amount of tourists yearly. Limited acceptance of reuse and recovery, water scarcity, and untapped potential for resource valorization.	Mitigate and remove barriers to water and resource reuse while demonstrating their feasibility.	Enhance freshwater conservation by increasing industrial and agricultural water reuse through transforming wastewater into reclaimed water. Recovery of nutrients. Reuse potential for water, sludge and nitrogen.

Table 5. Overview of the general context of each Living Lab. (Continued)

LL	Key challenges	Main ambition	Circular Economy approach
East Frisia	Increasing water demand from the consumer groups population, industry and agriculture; untapped potential water resource allocation.	Testing improved treatment of process water for reuse in the dairy and food industry, long-term water demand assessment, and improving short-term water demand forecasts through smart metering.	Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water). The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential.
Flanders	High drinking and industrial water demand, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, and climate change-related problems such as droughts resulting in increased agricultural irrigation needs.	Flood management and transformation of its water system into a circular one, integrating the urban and natural water cycles to ensure a sustainable freshwater supply. Consider potential alternative water sources such as rainwater and stormwater runoff for agricultural reuse.	Urban stormwater reuse for agriculture. Also, develop a regional concept for improving and monitoring water smartness, with a focus on safe water reuse and enhancing the integration of natural water systems.
Bodø	Growing resident population and economy, increased pollution, untapped efficiency potential. Raise public awareness about climate change impacts on water and stormwater management.	Develop a sustainable plan for the new district and the relocation of the airport.	Production of energy through co-digestion from sewage sludge and organic waste in several municipalities from Bodø and Salten. Potential transformation of treated sludge into resources: compost, biopellets and biochar.

3.2 Identification of circular economy opportunities in Living Labs

The identification of the main circular opportunities in each LL was carried out since the start of the project and has been updated recently according to the new status of each LL. Table 6 summarizes the main circularities identified in each LL. The next section 3.2 will describe in detail these circularities and its involved stakeholders for each LL.

Table 6. List of circularities of each LL.

LL name	Circularity	Circularity identified	Description
Alicante	C1	Waste to Energy	Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion
	C2	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Increase of water reuse (overcoming barriers – technical, economical and governance)
	C3	Wastewater to Raw materials	Recovery of materials / byproducts: NaClO production through brine valorization
	C4	Waste to Raw materials	Zero waste - Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production)
	C5	Wastewater to Energy	Increase of energy production: microturbines
	C6	Wastewater to Raw materials	Hydrogen and oxygen production from reclaimed water and biogas
Lisbon	C7	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Urban water reuse for irrigation
	C8	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Industrial water reuse for food grade application
Venice	C9	Wastewater to Reclaimed water	Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse
	C10	Wastewater to Raw materials	Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production)
	C11	Wastewater Sludge Valorization	Exploit all potential of sludge valorization
East Frisia	C12	Process water to Reclaimed water	Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water). The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential.
	C13	Alternative water resources to Reclaimed water	Municipal/Industrial/Urban wastewater to reclaimed water

Table 6. List of circularities of each LL. (Continued)

LL name	Circularity	Circularity identified	Description
Flanders	C14	Stormwater to Reclaimed water	Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system
	C15	Indirect effluent to drinking water	Process water to feed drinking water treatment plants
	C16	Maximization of Drinking water	Maximization of production in drinking water treatment plant
Bodø	C17	Waste to Energy	Increase of energy production through biogas

3.2.1 Circularity prioritization in each Living Lab

This deliverable aims to identify the potential circularities within each LL, along with their respective stakeholders. Additionally, a comprehensive methodology assessment will be provided to guide LLs in monitoring their circularities and assessing the progress of their strategic agendas. Furthermore, in collaboration with LL owners and mentors, a specific circularity has been selected and prioritized for each LL (**C1, C7, C9, C12, C14 and C17**). The aim was to delve into the details of these prioritized circularities, evaluate their benefits and quantify relevant indicators as outlined in section 2.3 (whenever possible and in the best way possible). It is important to note that these prioritized circularities are either currently being implemented or planned for the near future.

3.2.2 Summary of indicators to be assessed at each circularity prioritized

Table 7. List of CE indicators calculated in each LL.

Indicator	Circularity					
	LL Alicante	LL Lisbon	LL Venice	LL East Frisia	LL Flanders	LL Bodø
	C1. Waste to energy. Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	C7. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation	C9. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse	C12. Process water to Reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water).	C14. Stormwater to Reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system	C17. Waste to Energy. Increase of energy production through biogas
Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT _{eff})	X	X	X	X	X	X
Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU)		X	X	X	X	
Reclaimed Water Production (RWP)			X	X	X	
Linear Water Losses (LWL)		X	X	X	X	
Water Storage Capacity (WSC)		X	X	X	X	
Water Footprint (WFP)	X		X	X	X	X

Table 7. List of CE indicators calculated in each LL. (Continued)

Indicator	Circularity					
	LL Alicante	LL Lisbon	LL Venice	LL East Frisia	LL Flanders	LL Bodø
	C1. Waste to energy. Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	C7. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation	C9. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse	C12. Process water to Reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water).	C14. Stormwater to Reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system	C17. Waste to Energy. Increase of energy production through biogas
Carbon Footprint (CFP)	X	X	X	X	X	X
Water-related materials' Recovery (WR)	X					X
Fertilizer Production Avoided (FPA)	X	X				X
Energy Consumption (E_{eff})	X	X	X	X	X	X
Energy Production (EP)	X					X
Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR)	X	X	X	X		X
Circular economy business Models in practice (BM_{CE})	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 7. List of CE indicators calculated in each LL. (Continued)

Indicator	Circularity					
	LL Alicante	LL Lisbon	LL Venice	LL East Frisia	LL Flanders	LL Bodø
	C1. Waste to energy. Improve and increase of energy production: codigestion	C7. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation	C9. Wastewater to Reclaimed water. Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse	C12. Process water to Reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water).	C14. Stormwater to Reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation through a subirrigation system	C17. Waste to Energy. Increase of energy production through biogas
Green Jobs (GJ)	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social Acceptance	X	X	X	X	X	X
Stakeholder Engagement	X	X	X	X	X	X
Awareness and increased understanding	X	X	X	X	X	X
Governance compliance	X	X	X	X	X	X

3.3 Circularity assessment

3.3.1 Living Lab Alicante

LL Summary

Table 8. Summary of LL Alicante.

“LL Alicante demonstrates successful circularity results in the water-energy-resources nexus by converting a WWTP into a biofactory, creating local opportunities and fostering strong stakeholder collaboration, despite challenges with gender balance and governance soundness due to limited funding. This LL shows a positive example for circularity and sustainable resource management.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL Alicante

- **Objective:** Transform the Rincón de León WWTP into a biofactory, promoting circular water, energy, and resource management.
- **Circularities identified (6):**
 - **Water circularity :**
 - Reclaimed water is produced for agriculture and urban irrigation.
 - Brine valorization via Selective Electrodialysis (SED) and Electrochlorination (EC) generates sodium hypochlorite for water treatment/disinfection.
 - Nutrient recovery (ammonia) enables biofertilizer production.
 - **Energy circularity:**
 - Co-digestion of sludge and organic waste increases biogas production for heat and energy production.
 - Microturbines recover energy from wastewater effluents.
 - **Waste circularity:**
 - Sludge is evaluated for use as biofertilizer or in cement production.
- **Impact across scenarios (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):**
 - Circularity prioritized: Waste to energy. Improve and increase of energy production: co-digestion
 - Carbon footprint reduction: -137,747 → -681 → -1,499,555 kg CO₂e/year.
 - Energy savings: Up to €1.4M/year.
 - Water footprint reduction: 116,472 → -661 → -1,133,146 m³/year.
 - Green jobs increase: 5 → 7 → 9 full-time positions.
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 16 stakeholders engaged; representativeness but gender imbalance (only 33% women).
 - Supportive social attitude towards water circularities; some resistance from farmers.
 - Governance challenges due to policy uncertainty and lack of funding.

Circularities identified

The main ambition of the Living Lab Alicante is to transform the Rincón de León WWTP into a biofactory, a facility generating valuable resources such as reclaimed water, energy and nutrients. This is being achieved by the implementation of innovative water-smart solutions that aim to boost circular economy in the WWTP (Figure 3).

The Rincón de León WWTP, where wastewater is treated, is also followed by a desalination plant that includes ultrafiltration membranes followed by reverse osmosis to remove salinity and **produce reclaimed water** that is currently being **used mainly for agriculture and other urban uses such as irrigation in green areas**. However, the brine that is generated as a result of the reverse osmosis treatment is currently considered waste and is discharged into the sea, with the potential environmental impacts associated. In the case of the Rincón de León WWTP (in the frame of B-WaterSmart) the brine is being valorised through a treatment process (at a pilot scale) that includes Selective Electrodialysis (SED) and electrochlorination (EC). The SED aims to separate monovalent ions (e.g. Na^+ , Cl^-) from divalent ions (e.g. Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}), with the divalent ions forming the dilute stream suitable for water reuse, whereas the monovalent ions go into the EC unit to **produce sodium hypochlorite** (NaClO) in-situ. NaClO is a common disinfectant widely used in water treatment facilities for cleaning membranes and water disinfection processes, for instance. This treatment train will enable increasing the production of reclaimed water up to 100%.

Moreover, a low thermal evaporation system (Cartridge EVAPorator) is being implemented at pilot scale to treat the rejected water generated after drying the sludge digestate and allow the **recovery of nutrients such as ammonia**. These nutrients can be **used as a biofertilizer** by nearby irrigation communities. In the case of the energy nexus circularities, a **co-digestion process** is operating mixing wastewater sludge and solid waste (i.e. food waste and ice cream fat) generated in the local industries to produce biogas. The biogas is used for **energy cogeneration** and the **residual heat** will feed the co-digestion process. The digestate sludge after dewatering is currently being used in the **cement production industry**, as the heat generated when drying the sludge can feed the production chain. Moreover, ashes can also be used for cement production. Furthermore, it has been identified that the biogas could be upgraded to **produce biomethane or energy** for local transport and city consumption, respectively.

The last circularity identified is a **microturbine** installed at the treated effluent line before discharge, which allows for **energy recovery** from the wastewater treatment process.

Figure 3. Complete map of the circularities of LL Alicante

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 9 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 9. List of stakeholders identified in LL Alicante.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category/ Sector	Circularity involved
Aguas de Alicante (AMAEM)	Operator and regulator of the wastewater treatment plant	Water industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C1, C6
Public water sanitation entity (EPSAR)	Public institution owner of the wastewater treatment facilities of Rincón de León.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	-
Alicante municipality (city hall)	City hall of Alicante	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	All
CEMEX	Cement industry. User of digested sewage sludge	Representatives of other sectors	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C1, C4
Mercalicante	Mercalicante is the food distribution center of the city of Alicante, providing food for over 1.9 million residents	Representatives of other sectors	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Waste	C1
Helados Alacant	Local industry that leads the frozen cream market in Spain	Representatives of other sectors	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Waste	C1
Medifer	Local industry trading fertilizers for agriculture	Agriculture company	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C4
Comunidad de regantes Alicante Norte	Community/cooperative that provides water for irrigation to farmers	Agriculture company	Observer	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C2
Sindicato de Riegos de la Huerta de Alicante	Community/cooperative that provides water for irrigation to farmers	Agriculture company	Observer	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C2

Table 9. List of stakeholders identified in LL Alicante. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category/ Sector	Circularity involved
Veolia Agriculture	Consulting/engineering company specialized in providing support to farmers and agriculture	Agriculture company	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C2, C4
University of Alicante	Local public university in Alicante	Research institute	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Energy	C1, C5
Vectalia	Vectalia is a business group based in Alicante specialized in mobility and facility services.	Representatives of other sectors	Observer	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	-
IBERDROLA	Spanish multinational electric utility company. It is one of the largest energy companies in the world and operates in numerous countries	Representatives of other sectors	Follower	Value Chain Stakeholders	Energy	C1, C5
Turbulent	Microturbines technology provider, belgian company specialized in microturbines design and development	Engineering company	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Energy	C5
CEVAP	CEVAP technology provider	Engineering company	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C4
Alicante Port	Port authority of Alicante	Engineering company	Observer	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	-

The LL Alicante has successfully fostered engagement and collaboration with all relevant stakeholders through a series of themed CoPs organized since the start of the project. These CoPs have facilitated meaningful interactions and dialogue amongst stakeholders, enabling the LL owner Aguas de Alicante (AMAEM) to actively incorporate their input and ideas into the development of the circular initiatives. The majority of stakeholders listed have a direct influence on the LL Alicante and play a pivotal role in shaping the circularities. AMAEM has also closely collaborated with these stakeholders to ensure their perspectives are considered and integrated effectively. In addition, other stakeholders such as communities of irrigators, Vectalia and the Port Authority, have assumed a supportive role in the project. While they may not be directly involved in testing the circularities within the project's scope, they have actively participated in different dissemination events and discussion boards. Their involvement has been mainly focused in disseminating their specific needs and requirements, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the LL landscape.

As seen in Figure 4, stakeholders are well-represented in various circularity environments such as city, industry, agriculture and port. However, it is important to note that there is currently a gap in stakeholder representation within the ecosystem category.

Figure 4. Complete map of stakeholders of LL Alicante.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Waste to energy. Improve and increase of energy production: co-digestion** (C1 - See Figure 5).

It needs to be highlighted that some of the indicators from the categories Economy and Business (i.e. Circular economy business Models in practice), Green Jobs and Social are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C1) are:

- **Baseline scenario** WWTP with some circular processes already ongoing: anaerobic digestion treatment in 1 anaerobic reactor (only sewage sludge) at full-scale (10 m³) and production of energy for own consumption.
- **Circular scenario** Introduction of a co-digestion pilot (1m³) treating sewage sludge and organic waste (i.e. food waste and/or ice-cream fat) and production of energy for own consumption.
- **Scale-up scenario** Increase co-digestion pilot in 4 full-scale reactors (full capacity in Rincón de León). Increase of energy production for own consumption and upgrading to produce electricity and biomethane to the municipal grid and urban transport, respectively.

Figure 5. Diagram of input and output flows for circularity C1. Waste to energy. Improve and increase energy production: co-digestion.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C1 are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. LL Alicante circularity (C1) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The energy production through biological processes can contribute to **SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy** and the co-digestion process using local organic waste from other industries can also promote new business opportunities in the municipality (**SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure**). Furthermore, introducing circularities that involve urban infrastructure such as converting a WWTP into a biofactory can foster **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities** and **SDG 13: Climate Action**.

According to available data and current operational status of the co-digestion pilot, some indicators were evaluated to monitor the circularity and expected results in the future scenario. More information regarding the CBM development will follow in Deliverable 4.4 “Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs”.

Water

Although the circularity is related to the energy nexus provided by wastewater treatment, the **Effective Wastewater Treatment** (WWT_{eff}) has been evaluated. This value is estimated to be constant in the near future and the expected ratio of wastewater treated complying with legal requirements (WWT_{eff}) is around **70%**.

In the case of the **Water Footprint** (WFP) in LL Alicante, it is only considered the blue indirect WFP, since co-digestion is the principal process evaluated in this circularity. In addition, the WFP is calculated per tonne of treated sludge.

Table 10. Results of the Water Footprint (WFP) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
WF _{ww}	m ³ year ⁻¹	116,472.29	-661.51	-1,133,146.35
TS	tn year ⁻¹	200,750.00	16.00	208,750.00
WFP_{ww}	m³ m⁻³	0.58	-41.34	-5.43

As seen in Table 10, the circular scenario is the lowest, since the pilot plant is smaller than the other ones. For the scale-up, its negative value is due to positive impact, common in WWTP.

Air

The **Carbon Footprint** (CFP) of the co-digestion process has a negative value (positive impact). This is due to the fact that producing energy through biogas cogeneration can avoid the consumption of electricity from the municipal network. The results of the CFP are as follows:

Table 11. Results of the Carbon Footprint (CFP) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
CFP _{co-digestion}	kg CO _{2eq} year ⁻¹	-137,747.15	-681.77	-1,499,555.30
W _{treated}	tn year ⁻¹	200,750.00	16.00	208,750.00
CFP	kg CO_{2eq} tn⁻¹	-0.69	-42.6	-7.18

As seen in Table 11, the circular scenario has a higher value as data is provided from a pilot and some consumables and electricity consumption have not been scaled-up yet. All the scenarios are considered promoters of circular economy with a clear improvement in the scale-up scenario.

Waste

The **Water-related materials' Recovery** (WR) indicator was evaluated for the digested sludge that could be used as a biofertilizer or for cement production. To evaluate that, sludge generation in the WWTP ($W_{i, re}$) and centrifuged digestate ($W_{i, in}$) were considered (Table 12). The results of WR are as follow:

Table 12. Results of the Water-related materials' Recovery (WR) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
$W_{i, re}$	kg year ⁻¹	17,000.00	1.35	17,677.46
$W_{i, in}$	kg year ⁻¹	200,750.00	16.00	208,750.00
WR	%	8.47	8.44	8.47

The ratio of sludge recovered for its reuse as a by-product is maintained constant in all the scenarios.

The **Fertilizer Production Avoided** (FPA) evaluation will allow us to determine the viability of using centrifuged sludge as a biofertilizer. However, this indicator couldn't be assessed as data on the sludge nutrient content is not yet available.

Energy

The following Table 13 shows the results for the **Energy Consumption** (E_{eff}) and **Energy Production** (EP) indicators:

Table 13. Results of the Energy Consumption (E_{eff}) and Energy Production (EP) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
$E_{co-digestion}$	kWh year ⁻¹	659,693.00	52.58	950,885.00
$W_{treated}$	tn year ⁻¹	200,750.00	16.00	208,750.00
$E_{eff, co-digestion}$	kWh tn⁻¹	3.29	3.29	4.56
E_{re}	kWh year ⁻¹	1,485,125.00	2,628.00	7,008,000.00
E_w	kWh year ⁻¹	659,693.00	52.58	950,885.00
EP	%	225.12	4,998.26	737.00

The energy consumption needed for the co-digestion process (E_{eff}) is demanding. Ratios can be seen per tonne of waste treated (i.e. sludge or sludge combined with organic waste). The ratio increases in the scale-up scenario, but also all of this demand can be covered with produced energy during the same process (EP). As mentioned above, there can be a misinterpretation of some indicators in the circular-scenario. In this case, the circular scenario ratio for EP is almost 7 times higher than the scale-up scenario due to some missing data during the pilot operation (some consumptions have been obtained assuming theoretical values).

Economy and business

The energy production during the co-digestion process can **avoid the consumption of electricity** from the municipal network. This can save up to 1,400,000€ per year in electricity consumption for the LL considering the scale-up scenario, which is about 4.7 times higher than the baseline scenario.

The production of biofertilizers from sludge treatment can also be a path of generating new revenues for the LL. However, this data is still not available and the potential revenue obtained from this by-product could not be evaluated. In addition, there is the possibility that the biofertilizer could not be used directly in agriculture and might need to be sold to a fertilizer industry to further adapt it for this purpose. In this scenario, the costs and business related would also depend on the willingness of the industry to buy such biofertilizer and at what cost.

The conversion model of the WWTP of Rincón de León into a biofactory can increase the new and modified **circular economy business models put into practice** (BM_{CE}). In the baseline scenario, apart from the conventional business model of the WWTP, 2 existing CBMs (i.e. reclaimed water production for irrigation and energy production through digestion of sewage sludge) were already ongoing. During the B-WaterSmart project, 1 of the previous models was upgraded (i.e. energy production through co-digestion) and also 2 new CBMs were considered (i.e. NaClO and ammonia production). The scale-up scenario adds to the previous circularities implemented during the project (3 in total) one new potential CBMs (i.e. biomethane/hydrogen production). The progress of the CBMs implementation can be seen in the following Table 14:

Table 14. Results of the Circular Economy Business Models (BM_{CE}) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
BM_c	No	2	3	4
BM_{tot}	No	3	5	6
BM_{CE}	%	66.67	60.00	66.67

Green Jobs

The LL Alicante employs 28 people to operate the facility. In the baseline scenario (before the start of the B-WaterSmart project), around 5 workers were dedicated to the reclaimed water production and the digestion processes. The number of **green jobs** (GJ) increases during the circular scenario, as 2 people from the pool are operating the pilots (e.g. co-digestion, CEVAP, SED and EC). The estimated target is to have at least 9 people working full time on the different circular processes once they are operating at full scale. As seen in Table 15 the ratio of green jobs will increase from 17.86% to 32.14%.

Table 15. Results of the Green Jobs (GJ) in LL Alicante for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
NGJ	No year ⁻¹	5	7	9
NJ	No year ⁻¹	28	28	28
GJ	%	17.86	25.00	32.14

Social acceptance

The phrases associated with more positive and negative stances regarding the level of social acceptance have been categorized in Table 16, yielding a fairly good level. Therefore, the supportive level has been assigned to the LL.

Table 16. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL Alicante.

Alicante	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
There is a positive attitude and a high interest in water-energy-waste circularities. The social acceptance of the use of reclaimed water in agriculture is increasing. It is believed that it is important to provide training in digital technologies to develop new tools and involve distribution chains to analyze consumer habits. Some participants even make proposals that are more advanced than the current legislation (that is a clear sign of acceptance). Lack of awareness is considered a problem to be solved through correct communication and education. The younger population is considered the most open about innovative water solutions.	Representatives of agriculture and industry are somewhat more skeptical due to financial and legislative barriers. Between these two sectors, farmers are the hardest to convince because, in the industrial world, incentives could increase the level of acceptance.
SUPPORTIVE	

Stakeholder engagement

In the LL of Alicante, 5 collaborative activities were carried out, with the participation of 58 individuals. It is noteworthy that the participation was not equitable, as 76% of the participants were men. In none of the 3 Communities of Practice (CoP) nor in the 2 Focus Groups (FG), there was at least 40% female representation (the highest achieved was 33% in the first focus group). Analyzing the questionnaire results, a high level of participation was observed, resulting in an "Empowered" positioning with an average score of 4.6. On one hand, the aspect most positively evaluated by participants was the perception that they could express themselves spontaneously and without filters during meetings. On the other hand, participants highlighted two areas for improvement: the integration of all ideas and

perspectives during discussions and the effectiveness of meetings in motivating participants to take actions within their own organizations/daily life.

Awareness and increased understanding

According to the questionnaires answered by participants in various activities, regarding this specific indicator, a level of "full understanding" was achieved, with an average score of 4.6. The aspect most appreciated was the clarity of the presentations and speakers, while a lower score was given to understanding the perspectives of stakeholders.

Governance soundness

Based on the analysis of Alicante LL self-assessment (D.5.5), a neutral level has been established for the governance soundness indicator, obtaining a rather low final score of 45.83. Despite some relevant principles achieving a high-performance score, the regulatory uncertainty and the lack of policy coherence in the Alicante Living Lab context have a cascading negative effect on other key areas. This leads, for instance, to a lack of funding and an uneven distribution of water resources, which ultimately undermine the implementation of water-smart solutions.

Table 17. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL Alicante.

B-WaterSmart LLS	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governance Soundness
LL Alicante	23	$(23-12/36-12)*100$	45.83	Neutral

In conclusion, the LL of Alicante serves as an example of embracing circularity within the water-energy-resources nexus. By converting a WWTP into a biofactory, not only does it demonstrate a beneficial approach, but it also creates numerous local opportunities and fosters collaborations with stakeholders and communities. Indeed, this LL has achieved a very good level regarding stakeholder engagement, even if it is important to highlight the lack of gender balance. On the other hand, the governance soundness has been adversely affected by the lack of funding. However, this innovative initiative sets a positive precedent for other regions to follow in their pursuit of circularity and sustainable resource management.

3.3.2 Living Lab Lisbon

LL Summary

Table 18. Summary of LL Lisbon.

“LL Lisbon is a strong example of circularity in water reclamation production and reuse, improving water efficiency and resource management. Pioneering Portuguese legislation on reclaimed water, along with well-defined roles, supports the successful implementation of smart water solutions.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL Lisbon

- **Objective:** Enhance water reuse efficiency in Lisbon to address climate change risks and reduce dependence on distant freshwater sources.
- **Circularities identified (2):**
 - Reclaimed water for urban irrigation: Treated wastewater undergoes sand filtration, microfiltration, ultrafiltration, and chlorine disinfection to meet Class A water quality standards.
 - Smart water tools:
 - Algorithm for chlorine decay modeling to ensure safe water transport.
 - Risk assessment tool for water reuse in non-potable applications.
 - Industrial water reuse: Testing potable water reuse for the beverage industry using ozone, reverse osmosis, and activated carbon filtration
- **Impact across scenarios** (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):
 - Circularity prioritized: Wastewater to reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation
 - Reclaimed water usage for irrigation: 0 → 1.15M → 4M m³/year.
 - Water losses reduction: From 3,759 to <1,100 m³/year/km.
 - Carbon footprint reduction: Expected to drop below 0.10 kg CO₂eq/m³.
 - Green jobs: Increase from 2 to 7 full-time positions.
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 10 stakeholders engaged; representativeness and gender-balance.
 - Supportive social attitude towards water circularities; low awareness of scarcity.
 - Portugal’s pioneering legislation supports strong governance and clear regulatory roles but lacks a dedicated reclaimed water utility, slowing full implementation

Circularities identified

The smart-water challenge of the Lisbon LL derives from the dependency on distant freshwater resources which, under the existing climate change scenario, represents a risk for the growing population and economy. The green-blue infrastructure is a solution applied in Lisbon for tackling climate change impacts related to droughts, floods and heat waves. As reclaimed water is a sustainable source, largely independent of climate uncertainty, it can contribute to reducing pressure

on strategic freshwater resources and to allow resources' recovery, such as phosphorus. The Lisbon LL solutions and processes address this challenge by facilitating safe water reuse and increasing water-energy-phosphorus efficiency, improving Lisbon's climate readiness and resilience regarding water scarcity (Figure 7).

Lisbon's first circularity aims to **use reclaimed water** from urban WWTPs **for urban green areas irrigation**. The production of reclaimed water within the Lisbon LL pilot (AdTA's Beirolas resource recovery plant) is carried out through a sequence of treatment processes at the WWTP, through the following scheme: treated wastewater; sand filtration; microfiltration; and ultrafiltration. Next, the addition of chlorine to the reclaimed water provides a disinfection residual, a key barrier for water microbial stability as the reclaimed water travels in the distribution networks. This treatment scheme allows the production of reclaimed water with adequate quality for unrestricted urban irrigation (Class A, on a A to D scale, being A the best quality water, as established in the Portuguese Decree-Law 119/2019).

The **Lisbon LL solutions** address this circularity as follows:

(A) Safe water reuse

- Tool #24 – This tool implements a new, innovative algorithm for modeling chlorine decay, as a function of key water quality parameters, as the reclaimed water travels in distribution networks, on top of a standard hydraulic model. The tool works in conjunction with tool #25 by assessing transport and distribution risk of reclaimed water in candidate supply/demand combinations.
- Tool #27 – This tool implements a user-friendly risk assessment framework based on the latest ISO standards and EU Regulation, for water reuse in non-potable uses. It has been designed specifically to evaluate the candidate supply/demand combinations produced by tool #25, with which it works in tandem; it can also work as a stand-alone app.

(B) Water-energy-phosphorus efficiency

- Tool #25 – This tool implements a novel matchmaking framework for formulating and assessing candidate combinations of two or more supplies, including reclaimed water, in satisfying non-potable water demands in urban or regional contexts, to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options. The framework allows for essential assessment variables such as volume availability, cost, energy, carbon footprint or nutrient content to be factored in.
- Tool #17 – This tool implements a curated set of specifically designed metrics for the strategic and tactical prioritization of regional or urban supply/demand solutions involving potable and non-potable water. It has been tailored to the decisional problem laid out by tool #25, which produces candidate supply/demand combinations.

On the second hand, the **reclaimed water production for industrial reuse** is also being explored (Technology #1), with the development of a protocol for safe potable reuse in the beverage industry. The continuous 24/7 pilot plant for potable water reuse – an ozone and reverse osmosis plant further upgraded to include an activated carbon filter column – is being tested with different treatment

schemes to compare different pretreatments of reverse osmosis towards operational performance and water quality.

Figure 7. Complete map of the circularities of LL Lisbon.

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 19 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 19. List of stakeholders identified in LL Lisbon.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Câmara Municipal Lisboa (CML)	As a local administration, the Lisbon Municipality (CML) has powers in the areas of social action, environment, communications, external cooperation, culture and science, consumer protection, sports, education, energy, rural and urban equipment, housing, spatial planning and urbanism, heritage, municipal police, promotion of development, civil protection, basic sanitation, health, leisure and transport. Related to climate change, the municipality has a department to manage specifically cross-cutting policies in this framework, namely planning and managing the city's water use.	Public authority	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	C7
LNEC	LNEC is the largest Portuguese applied research institute in the field of civil engineering and related environmental areas, combining R&DI with advanced specialized consultancy, advanced training and support to the industry, and contributing to policy, regulation and standardization in several areas.	Research institute	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	C7
BASEFORM	Baseform is a software company focused in the water sector. In Lisbon LL, Baseform is a solution provider responsible for developing the software for the risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modeling in the distribution network, WEP balance and decision-support tools.	Representatives of other sectors	Core co-creator	Internal Stakeholders	Software	C7

Table 19. List of stakeholders identified in LL Lisbon. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Garden owners (others than CML)	Potential public and private users for a system expansion scenario.	End-user	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	C7
Municipalities from the Lisbon Metropolitan Area	Local administration.	Public authority	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	C7
Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA)	Águas do Tejo Atlântico is the water utility enabler of Lisbon LL, providing real data (on wastewater treatment and water reclamation) for several tools and is responsible for conducting the pilot tests needed to develop the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in craft beer production.	Water industry	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C7 C8
Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres (EPAL)	EPAL is the water utility which operates in the production, transport and distribution of drinking water in Lisbon and other municipalities, it is the largest water utility in Portugal, covering approximately 2.8 million consumers.	Water industry	Observer	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C7
Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente (APA) / ARH Tejo	The Portuguese Environment Agency (APA) is a public institute, within the scope of the Portuguese Environment and Climate Action Ministry. Its mission is to propose, develop and monitor public policies for the environment and sustainable development, in an integrated and participated manner, and in close cooperation with other sectoral policies and public and private entities.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C7

Table 19. List of stakeholders identified in LL Lisbon. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos (ERSAR)	ERSAR is the regulator of the water and waste services and the competent authority for drinking water quality. ERSAR's activity aims to ensure the guarantee and control of the quality of the services provided as well as the supervision of the prices, promoting the physical and economic accessibility of the services.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C7
Administração Regional de Saúde de Lisboa e Vale do Tejo (ARS LVT)	The mission of the Administração Regional de Saúde de Lisboa e Vale do Tejo is to guarantee access to quality healthcare for the population in its geographical area of intervention and to develop and promote activities in the field of public health, in order to guarantee the protection and promotion of people's health.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Health	C7 C8

In Lisbon, the previously identified stakeholders play an important role, each contributing to the success and impact of the reclaimed water production and use. The Lisbon Municipality (CML) is essential in its role of local administration, implementing public policies related to water use and environmental issues. The CML's involvement ensures the project aligns with municipal planning and contributes to sustainable urban development. The participation of LNEC in the project brings wide scientific and technological expertise, combining research, development, and consultancy in civil engineering and environmental areas. Águas do Tejo Atlântico (AdTA) is the water utility responsible for reclaimed water production in Lisbon. Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres (EPAL) is the water utility responsible for Lisbon's public drinking water supply system and eventually could manage the reclaimed water distribution network. Additionally, public authorities such as Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente (APA), Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos (ERSAR) and Administração Regional de Saúde de Lisboa e Vale do Tejo (ARS LVT) request the compliance with water quality standards, licensing, and health regulations to ensure the environmental, technical and economic sustainability of the project and the protection of public health. Baseform can provide technological solutions for effective operations management. Other public green areas' managers, private public garden owners, municipalities from the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, and potential end-users represent the broader community, influencing the reclaimed water system's expansion and adoption.

As seen in Figure 8, stakeholders are well-represented in various circularity environments such as city, industry, agriculture and the ecosystem of Lisbon. However, it is important to note that the stakeholder representation within the agriculture and ecosystem environment is not included in the identified circularities (C7 and C8), since it is focused on the provision for water services to urban and industrial uses.

Figure 8. Complete map of stakeholders of LL Lisbon.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Wastewater to reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation** (C7 - See Figure 9).

It needs to be highlighted that the indicators from the category Social are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C7) are:

- **Baseline scenario** Use of drinking water for non-potable uses in Lisbon (i.e. irrigation of urban green areas).
- **Circular scenario** Use of reclaimed water for non-potable uses in Parque Tejo, in Lisbon.
- **Scale-up scenario** Use of reclaimed water for non-potable uses in Lisbon (extended area).

Figure 9. Diagram of input and output flows for circularity C7. Wastewater to reclaimed water. Urban water reuse for irrigation.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C7 are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. LL Lisbon circularity (C7) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The use of reclaimed water for urban water reuse in Lisbon contributes to **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities** creating sustainable and resilient cities that integrate urban planning for responsible water use (**SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production**). It also contributes to **SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation** by producing the reclaimed water from wastewater for irrigation purposes. Moreover, the wastewater treatment and water reuse initiative aligns with **SDG 13: Climate Action** by fostering climate-resilient approaches to water resource management.

According to available data and current operational status of the application of reclaimed water in green urban areas, some indicators were evaluated to monitor the circularity and expected results in the future scenario. More information regarding the CBM development will follow in Deliverable 4.4 “Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs”.

Water

To analyze the **Effective Wastewater Treatment** (WWT_{eff}) it is needed to take into account that the volume of wastewater treated in the WWTP ($V_{treatment}$) includes more municipalities than Lisbon, but the wastewater produced in the LL scope (WW) considers only the city of Lisbon. This is why the results give values more than 100%. Regarding the circular scenario, the results of the volume of WW complying with legal requirements has not been published yet. CML is not a water utility, so this is a context indicator in the strategic planning.

Table 20. Results of the Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT_{eff}) in LL Lisbon for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
$V_{treatment}$	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	69,800,230.0 0	-	72,000,000.0 0
WW	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	54,085,000.0 0	64,264,236.0 0	53,980,370.0 0
WWT_{eff}	%	129	-	133

As shown in Table 20, this value is estimated to be constant in the near future and the expected ratio of wastewater treated complying with legal requirements (WWT_{eff}) is more than 100%.

The following Table 21 shows the **Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses** (RWnpU). The result of this indicator increase in circular and scale-up scenarios due to the objective of the circularity which is to increase the use of reclaimed water for non-potable uses such as urban irrigation or street washing.

Table 21. Results of Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU) in LL Lisbon for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
RW	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	0.00	1,149,750.00	4,000,000.00
npW	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	3,180,614.00	4,055,837.00	5,000,000.00
RWnpU	%	0	28	80

The **Linear Water Losses** (LWL) indicator is higher in the baseline scenario than in the scaled-up scenario, which is interpreted as an improvement in water efficiency and management when applying CE strategies and increasing the scale of the system. The Lisbon Strategic Plan for the linear losses in the scale-up scenario is expected to be minor than $1,100 \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$ by 2035. For the evaluation of this indicator an estimate of 10% water losses in the network has been considered for the circular scenario. The highest value in the circular scenario is due to the fact that the irrigation network is old and needs further maintenance and rehabilitation.

Table 22. Results of Lineal Water Losses (LWL) in LL Lisbon for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
V_{loss}	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	5,440,776.70	405,575.00	-
L_{net}	km	1,447.30	17.72	1,532.00
LWL	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$	3,759.00	22,888.00	<1,100

As shown in Table 22, an expected lower value of linear losses in the scale-up scenario indicates that the resource management practices and the circular approach are proving successful in reducing water losses in the infrastructure.

In terms of the **Water Storage Capacity** (WSC), for the moment it is not relevant but it is recommended to evaluate it in the scale-up scenario once the LL has established the storage capacity and the distribution network strategy.

Air

The **Carbon Footprint** (CFP) of the water distribution for irrigation purposes in the baseline scenario (using drinking water) has been obtained from Lisbon Sustainability Reports (EPAL, 2021; ERSAR, 2021) and is 0.14 kg CO₂eq m⁻³. In the scale-up scenario, which considers the irrigation with reclaimed water on a bigger scale, has been estimated as lower than 0.10 kg CO₂eq m⁻³. Regarding the circular scenario, there is no value yet as there exists no reclaimed water distribution network at the moment.

Waste

The **Fertilizer Production Avoided** (FPA) indicator couldn't be evaluated, but it has a future potential interest due to the evaluation of fertirrigation with reclaimed water. Thus, phosphorus recovered in reclaimed water could be of interest, as the water-energy-phosphorus nexus is of great importance in LL Lisbon, which has the objective of decreasing its footprint by improving the water supply and decreasing raw materials used by testing alternative sources.

Energy

The results for the **Energy Consumption** (E_{eff}) for the reclaimed water production is 0.70 kWh m⁻³ (estimated value), applicable to the circular and scale-up scenarios. In the baseline scenario, the energy consumption in drinking water supply is 0.55 kWh m⁻³ (EPAL, 2021). It is expected that the energy consumption for the reclaimed water distribution in the scale-up scenario will be lower than 0.5 kWh m⁻³.

Economy and business

Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR) has to be adapted as cost savings/balance between drinking water supply and reclaimed water supply. The former is OPEX and the second is CAPEX + OPEX.

The conversion model of Lisbon city into a more circular one by promoting the use of reclaimed water to avoid freshwater consumption can increase the new and modified **circular economy BMs put into practice** (BM_{CE}). In the baseline scenario, only 1 business model was already ongoing (drinking water supply). During the B-WaterSmart project, 1 new CBM (reclaimed water supply for irrigation) was introduced. The scale-up scenario continues with the same CBMs regarding irrigation in Lisbon. The progress of the CBMs implementation can be seen in the following table:

Table 23. Results of the Circular Economy Business Models put into practice (BM_{CE}) in LL Lisbon for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
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BM _c	No	0	1	1
BM _{tot}	No	1	2	2
BM _{CE}	%	0	50	50

Green Jobs

In the baseline scenario, CML has no workers dedicated to reclaimed water use. The number of **green jobs** (GJ) is estimated to increase from 2 to 7 full-time equivalent jobs (2 engineers and 5 operators) with the scale-up.

Social acceptance

The phrases linked to both positive and negative perspectives on the extent of social acceptance have been organized into Table 24, resulting in a favorable assessment. Consequently, the label of "supportive level" has been assigned to LL.

Table 24. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL Lisbon.

Lisbon	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
The perception of citizens is changing due to drought episodes in recent years. The media were focusing on the subject and documentaries were being made to raise awareness. In general, a positive attitude on the part of the population is recognized. Reclaimed water, for example, is considered a valid alternative for the irrigation of green spaces. There is general public confidence in water utilities and in the water authority and the water regulator.	There is still little awareness of the water scarcity.
SUPPORTIVE	

Stakeholder engagement

In the Living Lab (LL) of Lisbon, 5 collaborative activities involving 162 participants were carried out. The overall participation demonstrated gender balance, with 41% men and 59% women. Upon analyzing the questionnaire results, a commendable level of participation emerged, leading to a "Collaborative" rating with an average score of 4.4. On the one hand, participants highly appreciated the constructive handling of differences and conflicts among participants. On the other hand, an area for improvement was identified: the effectiveness of meetings in motivating participants to take actions within their own organizations.

Awareness and increased understanding

Based on the questionnaires filled out by participants across different activities, a level of "aware" was obtained for this particular indicator, garnering an average score of 4.2.

Governance soundness

Portugal was the first European country with legislation (2019 decree-law) fully aligned with the relevant ISO standards as well as the 2020 EU regulation on water reuse in agriculture and is inspiring other EU member states. There are aspects that can be improved in the implementation of water reuse systems, of course, but there is a sound governance framework for water reuse in Portugal. Roles and responsibilities of the regulators are clearly defined. Licensing by the Environmental authority, with the opinion of the health authority, and ERARS regulates the water service. Urban water reuse is pioneering in Portugal. To facilitate the business model implementation is necessary to deal with the specificity in Lisbon: one water utility, one wastewater utility licensed for reclaimed water production but still no dedicated utility for reclaimed water distribution, which is slowing down the implementation of water reuse projects.

Table 25. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL Lisbon.

B-WaterSmart LLs	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governance Soundness
LL Lisbon	10	$(10-5/15-5)*100$	50	Neutral

Finally, it should be noted that the LL of Lisbon serves as an example of circularity dedicated to water reclamation. Overall, the findings suggest that circular and scale-up approaches contribute to enhanced water efficiency, resource management and circular economy practices in Lisbon. The pioneering Portuguese legislation on reclaimed water, combined with the clear definition of roles and responsibilities, facilitates the implementation of smart water solutions.

3.3.3 Living Lab Venice

LL Summary

Table 26. Summary of LL Venice.

“LL Venice’s circularity assessment highlights gains in reclaimed water production, reducing treated water discharge to the sea, and supporting industrial reuse, which contributes to water efficiency, resource recovery, and job creation. Although improvements are needed in data fragmentation and policy coherence, social acceptance of water reuse is strong. High quality water recovery has been demonstrated, offering a reliable solution for industrial use under challenging climate change conditions, and with greater energy efficiency in the scale-up scenario.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL Venice

- **Objective:** Improve water reuse for industrial and agricultural applications, reduce treated water discharge to the sea, and enhance resource recovery at the Fusina WWTP.
- **Circularities identified (3):**
 - Reclaimed water for industrial reuse: A three-stage treatment process (ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, electro-deionization) produces high-purity water for industries.
 - Nutrient recovery: Ammonium sulfate is recovered from wastewater for fertilizer production, reducing nitrogen discharge and increasing biogas generation.
 - Wastewater sludge valorization: Decision support tools evaluate the best reuse pathways, including energy recovery, composting, and agriculture applications
- **Impact across scenarios** (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):
 - Circularity prioritized: Wastewater to reclaimed water. Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse
 - Reclaimed water production: 0 → 8,760 → 2.63M m³/year.
 - Freshwater savings in industry: 0 → 0.1% → 33% reduction.
 - Carbon footprint reduction: Expected to drop from 0.02 to 0.04 kg CO₂eq/m³.
 - Green jobs: Increase from 0 to 4 full-time positions.
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 26 stakeholders engaged; representativeness and gender-balance.
 - High social acceptance for water reuse, but resistance remains on sludge valorization.
 - Neutral governance soundness with data fragmentation and policy coordination issues.

Circularities identified

The LL Venice aims to address environmental challenges from human activities and climate change, implementing resource recovery and CE strategies to improve the region's delicate balance, tackling challenges such as water scarcity and untapped resource valorization potential. Proposed solutions in the LL include treating the **wastewater to obtain reclaimed water**, increasing the **industrial and**

agricultural water reuse. Then, with the B-WaterSmart solutions, the WWTPs will act as a biofactory by producing reclaimed water, recovering nutrients and valorizing wastewater sludge (i.e. energy, fertilizers, etc.) (Figure 11).

The current situation of LL Venice is that the Fusina WWTP discharges to the sea. For this reason, the first circularity aims to produce **reclaimed water for industrial water reuse.** The process is carried out through a sequence of technological treatments. In the first place, a three-stage pilot (ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis and electro-deionization) takes place. Ultrafiltration is used to remove particles and macromolecules, reverse osmosis further reduces contaminants by removing smaller molecules and ions and electro-deionization completes the process by removing remaining ions and producing high purity water. All streams have been tested to assess the suitability of the different qualities for the several industrial needs. The convenience of the most effective treatments chain for the actual industrial requirements, will be evaluated also for energy consumption and other collateral costs since there is the opportunity/possibility that it can replace the current UV disinfection system (first part of PIF reclamation treatment plant).

The PIF plant is located at the effluent of the Fusina WWTP. Due to results obtained it is clear that the sequence of treatments for the production of reclaimed water for industrial reuse can be applied directly to the effluent from the Fusina WWTP, before entering the PIF system. However it could happen that, due to several reasons (i.e. authority requirements or over-precautionary approach), the sequence of treatments for the reclaimed water production for industrial reuse is applied downstream of the UV treatment, just after the first step of the PIF treatment. The PIF treatment was created for the non-potable reuse of Fusina effluent, the industrial reuse was theoretically included but the sequence of treatments was not adapted for this reuse. In theme of water saving and reuse, the PIF plant is instead very adapted to produce effluent for agricultural reuse; this kind of reuse is investigated at a regional scale thanks to the strategic informatic tools (specifically the tool #16) developed by the LL with an active CoP collaboration.

At the level of **nutrient recovery**, the second circularity fosters practices in the wastewater treatment to recover nitrogen and produce salts (ammonium sulfate) to be provided for agricultural applications. For this purpose, two different stripping technologies are implemented and compared to treat concentrated liquid streams from the sludge anaerobic digestion and co-digestion, with the objective of choosing the most convenient from a technical and economical point of view. The co-digestion will be tested with a balanced combination of liquid domestic waste and sludge to increase nutrient recovery and energy saving through the increase of biogas production. The expectation for the ammonium sulfate quality is high, with some levels of purity even major than the commercial products. The water that has undergone the stripping waste of the process is recirculated at the WWTP inlet but with a lower nitrogen load, with respect to original concentrated streams, allowing energy savings and emission reductions. The co-digestion tested at pilot-lab scale by several combinations of balancing between liquid domestic waste and sludge can enhance nitrogen recovery while increasing biogas production and the energy saving.

The third circularity considers **wastewater sludge** and the possibility to valorise it through the most sustainable treatment and disposal solutions, using the decision support system, developed under B-WaterSmart (tool #19), that allows to take into account all the key variables (qualitative-quantitative data, regulation, territory...) and evaluate the different **valorization pathways** in relation to the socio-economical and geographical context. For example, producing energy to supply **energy** to the

municipal grid or to themselves, generating **fertilizers** (i.e. from composting) and/or stabilizing the treated sludge for **agriculture reuse** (carbon replenishment for depleted solids), among others.

Figure 11. Complete map of the circularities of LL Venice.

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 27 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 27. List of stakeholders identified in LL Venice.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Veritas S.p.A.	Public multi-utility responsible for Integrated Water Services and waste management for a territory of 51 municipalities and 1 million inhabitants.	Water industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Veneto Region	Main regional authority - responsible for the National Law contextualization in the territory (3 Directions involved).	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
ARPAV	Regional technical agency for the Environmental protection and control (4 Departments involved).	Public authority	Core co-creator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Metropolitan city of Venice	Local public administrative authority for the integrated environmental management and pollution control.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C11
Venice Lagoon Basin Council	Territorial authority for the Integrated Water Services (Basin Council or EGATO) responsible for transferring the targets established at national level by ARERA into territory plans.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C9, C11
ANBI Veneto	National Association of Consortia for territory and irrigation waters management and protection.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9*
Acque Risorgive Reclamation Consortium	Local consortium for territory and irrigation waters management and protection.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9
Confindustria Veneto Est (ex Cofindustria Venezia)	Industrial category association; expression of the national Confindustria in the regional territory.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9

Table 27. List of stakeholders identified in LL Venice. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Porto Marghera Industrial Zone Organization	Industrial category association of Porto Marghera zone.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9
Viveracqua	Regional Consortium of Integrated Water Service Utilities.	Water industry	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Veneto Agricoltura	Regional Agency for Innovation in the primary sector.	Research institute	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Confagricoltura Venezia	Agricultural category association; expression of the General Confederation of Italian Agriculture in the Venice province.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Coldiretti	Agricultural category association	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
CIC - <i>Consorzio Italiano Compostori</i>	Italian Composting and Biogas Association	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C11
Venice University - Ca' Foscari	University	Research institute	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Verona University	University	Research institute	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C9, C10, C11
LeNS Landscape Enterprise Network	Commercial partnerships to foster sustainable practice for resilient territories.	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C11

Table 27. List of stakeholders identified in LL Venice. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
SIFA s.c.p.a.	Consortium company, of which Veritas is the majority shareholder, concessionaire of the Veneto Region for the creation and management of the Fusina Integrated Project.	Project & Management Company	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9
ETRA	Public multi-utility responsible for Integrated Water Services and waste management for a territory of 61 municipalities and 600.000 inhabitants.	Water industry	Partner	Internal Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Depuracque	Waste and wastewater treatments provider and/or management.	Engineering company	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C10
Hydrotech Engineering	Water treatment technology provider.	Engineering company	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9
Engineering Ingegneria Informatica	ICT - Digital transformation company	Engineering company	Partner	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water; Resources ; Waste	C9, C10, C11
Port industries	Industries/industrial activities of the nearby Porto Marghera industrial Area (12 Companies involved).	End-user	Core co-creator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C9
Regional University	University.	Research institute	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C11
Agricultural company	Agricultural company equipped with treatment plants for the direct/indirect valorization of sewage sludge in agriculture.	Agriculture company	Follower	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources; Waste	C11
Water consultant	Regional consultant in hydrological, hydraulic and reclamation sector.	Engineering company	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C9

Several stakeholders have an active participation in LL Venice, contributing to the success, implementation and expansion of the identified circularities. The most important is Veritas S.p.A., a public multi-utility entity which serves as a partner, overseeing integrated water services and waste management across the territory and being the main company to manage the WWTP of interest in the Venice circularities.

Furthermore, Veneto Region, as the principal regional authority, contextualizes national laws locally, emphasizing circular practices in water, resources, and waste. Also ARPAV, a regional environmental agency, is a core co-creator within the LL Venice framework, contributing expertise to circularities associated with water, resources, and waste. The Metropolitan City of Venice and the Venice Lagoon Basin Council collaborate as value network stakeholders, focusing on integrated environmental management and water-related circular practices.

Industry associations like Confindustria Veneto Est and Industrial Porto Marghera zone organization and consortia for irrigation water management, like ANBI Veneto and Acque Risorgive Reclamation Consortium, actively contribute to circular initiatives in water. Viveracqua, the regional consortium of water service utilities, plays a key role in circular practices across water, resources, and waste.

In summary, LL Venice is shaped by the collaborative efforts of stakeholders spanning public authorities, industry, and agricultural associations, and research institutions, all working towards a comprehensive circular approach in water, resources and waste management.

Illustrated in Figure 12, stakeholders play diverse roles across all the circularity domains (city, industry, agriculture and ecosystem).

Figure 12. Complete map of stakeholders of LL Venice.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Wastewater to reclaimed water. Increase of industrial and agricultural water reuse** (C9 - See Figure 13), evaluating in particular the industrial reuse.

It needs to be highlighted that some of the indicators from the categories Economy and Business (i.e. Circular economy business Models in practice), Green Jobs and Social are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C9) are:

- Baseline scenario** Fusina WWTP with some circular processes already ongoing, considering only treatments (filtration + ultraviolet) partially avoided with the installation of the reclamation plant. Marine discharge of the treated water.
- Circular scenario** Introduction of a pilot plant for reclaimed water production with a three-stage pilot to be tested: ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, and electro-deionization. Reclaimed water use for industrial purposes.
- Scale-up scenario** Upgrade the reclamation plant, based on pilot results, to produce more reclaimed water and furtherly reduce marine discharge. Reclaimed water will be used for industrial purposes.

Figure 13. Diagram of input and output flows for circularity C9. Wastewater to reclaimed water. Increase of industrial water reuse.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C9 are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. LL Venice circularity (C9) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The circularity of transforming wastewater into reclaimed water for industrial and agricultural use significantly contributes to SDGs 6, 11, 9 and 13. By promoting sustainable water use and reducing pollution, it aligns with **SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation**. On the other hand, reusing reclaimed water in industries fosters sustainable urbanization, mitigates water scarcity and supports efficient water management, contributing to **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities**. In addition, the innovation in water treatment technologies and the promotion of resource-efficient industrial practices is related with **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure**. Furthermore, this circular approach addresses the impact of climate change on water resources, reduces reliance on traditional freshwater sources and minimizes energy consumption, aligning with **SDG 13: Climate Action**.

Based on the existing data and the ongoing operational status of the reclaimed water production pilot plant, several indicators were assessed to track the circularity and anticipated outcomes in the future scenario. Additional details on the development of Circular Business Models (CBM) will be provided in Deliverable 4.4 "Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs".

Water

The **Effective Wastewater Treatment** (WWT_{eff}) is 100% since all the wastewater produced in the city ($38,000,000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$) is treated in the WWTP and complies with legal discharge requirements. Additionally, in the scale-up scenario, a higher compliance in treated wastewater will be guaranteed for a flow ratio of 7% (i.e. the volume of treated wastewater that is sent to produce reclaimed water).

Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU) and **Reclaimed Water Production** (RWP) are shown in the following Table 28. The first one would be interesting in helping to understand the amount of reclaimed water that could replace the direct use of potable water for non-potable uses, but it does not apply to this case; instead it is interesting to interpret it

in terms of the amount of reclaimed water that saves freshwater (now used to produce industrial water), freshwater that in turn can be used to produce potable water. The results show that the use of reclaimed water for industrial uses in Venice has the potential to reduce freshwater consumption in the industrial sector by about 33%.

The **Reclaimed Water Production** (RWP) increases in the scale-up scenario since it is expected to produce more reclaimed water.

Table 28. Results of the Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU) and Reclaimed Water Production (RWP) in LL Venice for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
RW	m ³ year ⁻¹	0	8,760.00	2,628,000.00
npW	m ³ year ⁻¹	8,000,000.00	8,000,000.00	8,000,000.00
RWnpU	%	0.00	0.11	32.85
V _{reclaimed}	m ³ year ⁻¹	0.00	8,760.00	2,628,000.00
TWW	m ³ year ⁻¹	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00
RWP	%	0.00	0.02	6.92

The **Linear Water Losses** (LWL) would also be important to analyze, since the losses of the pipelines are useful to improve the water infrastructure and efficiency but, more important for drinking water existing distribution system, they are out of the boundaries of this assessment, since reclamation water distribution infrastructures are only partially present and their use/upgrade is strictly dependent on the final end-users scenario.

Regarding **Water Storage Capacity** (WSC), it is currently not a relevant consideration, but it is advisable to assess it in the scale-up scenario once the LL has established both the storage capacity and the distribution network. At this point, evaluating WSC becomes more important to ensure the effective management and distribution of reclaimed water in a larger-scale implementation.

A WWTP can be viewed as a CE system for itself, given its purpose to regenerate wastewater, making it suitable for reuse or safe reintroduction into the natural environment. The **Water Footprint** (WFP) of the WWTP considers water consumption (almost zero in WWTPs), the avoided impact of the reclaimed water production and the indirect impact of the WWTP (e.g. energy and chemicals consumption). In this case the impact of the wastewater treatment is not considered as it is discharged to the sea and not within the same watershed.

Table 29. Results of the Water Footprint (WFP) in LL Venice for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
WF _{ww}	m ³ year ⁻¹	11,937.54	-8,768.62	-2,605,334.22
TWW	m ³ year ⁻¹	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00
WFP _{ww}	m ³ m ⁻³	0.00	0.00	-0.07

As it is seen in Table 29, circular and scale-up's WFP have a negative value as reclaimed water production can compensate for the impacts. However, the WFP is an estimation, as there is still some missing data from the reclaimed water production process that could change the results. The principal reason is that the quantitative scenario referring to the pilot was not still completely available at the writing moment, chemical consumption had not ended yet and for what concerns energy the system was too small to justify an energy counter installation.

Air

The **Carbon Footprint** (CFP) associated with the WWTP and the production of reclaimed water shows consistently low values across all scenarios. The results of the Carbon Footprint assessment are as follows:

Table 30. Results of the Carbon Footprint (CFP) in LL Venice for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
CF _{ww}	m ³ year ⁻¹	711,175.00	0.00	1,504,257.02
TWW	m ³ year ⁻¹	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00
CFP	kg CO _{2eq} m ⁻³	0.02	0.00	0.04

As seen in Table 30, the circular scenario is zero not valorised since an energy counter has not been installed, due to the too small size of Pilot and the related unreliability of consumptions to be compared to or used for the scaling up.

Energy

The following Table 31 shows the results for the **Energy Consumption** (E_{eff}) at the WWTP:

Table 31. Results of the Energy Consumption (E_{eff}) in LL Venice for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
E_{ww}	kWh year ⁻¹	1,775,168.00	0.00	3,754,801.12
TWW	m ³ year ⁻¹	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00	38,000,000.00
E_{eff}	kWh m ⁻³	0.05	0.00	0.10

The E_{eff} is higher in the scale-up scenario, due to the increase of the production of reclaimed water processes compared to the baseline scenario. The circular scenario is currently reported as zero since the system's size did not justify the installation of an energy counter. Also in this case, the quantitative scenario data related to the pilot is partial (limited to data relevant for the case study purposes) and energy consumption is lacking.

Economy and business

In general, industries located in areas where water is scarce, such as in Venice, may find it advantageous to purchase reclaimed water for their operations. The advantage is even stronger today in the context of droughts that compromise the quantity and quality of surface freshwater, since reclaimed water produced from WWTP effluent guarantees both quantity and quality over time. The assessment of the **Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR)** indicator is still ongoing, as negotiations are underway to assess needs and identify the appropriate CBM.

The conversion model of the WWTP of Venice into a more circular one by producing reclaimed water and recovering nutrients can increase the new and modified **circular economy BMs put into practice** (BM_{CE}). In the baseline scenario, only 1 business model of the WWTP existed (the WW treatment itself). During the B-WaterSmart project, 2 new models (reclaimed water production for industrial reuse and nitrogen recovery) were included. The scale-up scenario adds 2 more CBMs connected with the two DSS-tools development (one for the effluent agricultural/urban reuse, the other for recovering nutrient and carbon or energy by the sludge valorisation) and a potential fortification of one of the 2 new developed (nitrogen recovery). The progress of the CBMs implementation can be seen in the following table:

Table 32. Results of the Circular Economy Business Models put into practice (BM_{CE}) in LL Venice for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
BM_{c}	No	0	2	4
BM_{tot}	No	1	3	5
BM_{CE}	%	0.00	66.67	80.00

Green Jobs

The LL Venice has people employed to operate the facility. In the baseline scenario (before the start of the B-WaterSmart project), there were no workers dedicated to the reclaimed water production. The number of **green jobs** (GJ) increases during the circular scenario, as 1-2 people from the pool are operating the pilots (e.g. reclaimed water). The estimated target in the scale-up scenario is to increase the % of green jobs once the 3 identified circularities and its CBMs will be operating at full scale. However, since a stable profile for the scale up does not exist yet, these estimations can not be more precise at the moment.

Social acceptance

The statements expressing both positive and negative perspectives on the level of social acceptance have been classified into Table 33, resulting in a satisfactory level. Consequently, the label "supportive level" has been designated for the LL.

Table 33. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL Venice.

Venice	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
There is high sensitivity to water recovery and reuse practices. No active resistance has been registered in the tests that were launched in Venice. The local government supports the saving of water and the resistances on the industrial use can be solved with the results of the demonstrative phase. Good levels of acceptance of regenerated water are expected at all levels of society. There is also good acceptance for the sludge valorisation targets and effluent reuse for industrial targets.	There is still a collective resistance to the valorization of sludge.
SUPPORTIVE	

Stakeholder engagement

In the Living Lab (LL) of Venice, 37 collaborative meetings/activities were conducted for a total of 357 participations distributed among the about 40 individuals of the CoP. On average the overall participation was balanced by gender (50% women vs 50% men). The inclusion of stakeholders was maximum since the beginning of the CoP constitution, thanks to the involvement right from the start of the top roles of all key organizations and the total avoiding of a top-down approach which could have paralyzed the freedom of the parties, making the atmosphere excessively formal. This is the reason on one side of the high stakeholders commitment obtained and on the other of the impossibility to adopt tout-court the Cop-assessing model chosen by the project.

Awareness and increased understanding

To understand the level of awareness among CoP participants regarding water challenges and the efficient use of water resources, in particular wastewater and sludge, a social

scientist from KWR participated in a CoP meeting and interviewed 3 CoP participants on December 5th, 2023. Based on the data collected, the level of awareness and understanding is scored as 5 - Full understanding. The Venice CoP is composed of experts from different public and private organizations with high level understanding of water problems and opportunities offered by different solutions. In fact, it is precisely this understanding that draws these experts to work together in the CoP. The CoP has the ambition to prove with sound data the effectiveness and safety of such solutions. This is reflected in the CoP discussion which revolves around technical aspects of the solutions being tested as a shared understanding of the problems and the potential of the solutions tested is clear to everybody. This was also confirmed by the interviewees who indicated the high value of the CoP as a platform to demonstrate the effectiveness and safety of the tested solutions as a way to foster their uptake. Interviewees also reported to have acquired new knowledge and deeper understanding of the tested solutions thanks to the CoP and indicated to be satisfied with the process and activities.

Governance soundness

Based on the analysis of the governance implications identified in D.5.5, Venice LL territorial governance has obtained a 70 final score, thus categorized as neutral under the governance soundness indicator. The principles with the lowest score are policy coherence, due to the lack of cross-sectoral policy coordination and vertical coherence, and data and information caused by fragmented data availability.

Table 34. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL Venice.

B-WaterSmart Ls	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governance Soundness
LL Venice	24	$(24-10/30-10)*100$	70	Neutral

In summary, the analysis of the water-related parameters in the Venice wastewater treatment scenarios reveals that gains are achieved through water reclamation, avoiding discharge from the WWTP to the sea, contributing to non-potable uses and enabling the circular economy. Overall, the analysis suggests positive trends in water efficiency, resource recovery, circular economy practices and job creation in the Venice wastewater management system.

Regarding the social and governance dimension, there is a high sensitivity towards water recovery and reuse practices, thanks in part to the absence of active resistance. However, there is room for improvement in terms of data fragmentation and the lack of policy coherence and vertical structure that, at least partially, can be solved by the adoption of the strategic informatics tools, the DSS supporting decision makers, developed by the LL within the BWS projects.

Briefly, the results obtained so far regarding this circularity have provided all the key elements to highlight the high value of this circularity and to enable its use. In fact, the pilot phases, tailored to address specific problems and needs of industrial end-users, have consistently documented high quality of recovered water. This circularity can address a quali-quantitative challenge that freshwater use, with its uncontrollable quali-quantitative and risk variation, cannot guarantee. A key solution (regardless of price) in these increasingly challenging climate scenarios.

Regarding the assessment of impacts (carbon footprint, energy consumption, etc.), since the pilot size could not guarantee the reliability of the data and assessments (especially regarding energy consumption), this assessment was carried out using the scale-up scenario of relative expected impact (EI3).

For impacts however, it should also be noted that comparisons among scenarios should be made with scenarios set for comparable goals (industrial quality and assurance). In this case, the baseline scenario is adequate for today's discharge to the sea, while the scale up scenario provides reclaimed water suitable for industrial processes. If the baseline scenario would provide the same microbiological assurance as the alternative, the circularity in question, its energy consumption would be far higher, even up to 4 times higher.

3.3.4 Living Lab East Frisia

LL Summary

Table 35. Summary of LL East Frisia.

“The circularity assessment in East Frisia’s dairy industry shows potential for increased water reuse without increasing fresh water demand, supporting future production expansion. Effective Cow Water Treatment consistently reaches 100%, though limited data on consumables affects footprint accuracy. Moreover, stakeholders demonstrate strong engagement and gender balance.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL East Frisia

- **Objective:** Increase water reuse in the dairy industry without increasing freshwater demand, enabling future production expansion.
- **Circularities identified (2):**
 - Cow water treatment: Vapor condensate (cow water) is reclaimed through biological, bio-physical, and membrane filtration (ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, UV disinfection).
 - Industrial water reuse: Processed reclaimed water is used for dairy operations, reducing dependency on freshwater.
 - Potential expansion: Future treatment of municipal and industrial wastewater for broader reuse applications
- **Impact across scenarios** (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):
 - Circularity prioritized: Process water to reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate
 - Reclaimed water production: 350,000 → 350,000 → 860,000 m³/year.
 - Freshwater savings: Up to 450,000 m³/year, improving water footprint (-0.41 m³ avoided per 1 m³ discharged cow water).
 - Carbon footprint remains low (3.7 → 0.4 → 18.1 kg CO₂eq/year), though energy demand increases for water treatment (0.51 → 1.36 → 1.28 kWh/m³).
 - Green jobs: Increase from 0 to 1 full-time employee at scale-up
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 8 stakeholders engaged; representativeness and gender-balance.
 - Strong support for water reuse, but concerns over food industry applications.
 - Governance requires clearer regulations for water reuse in dairy operations.

Circularities identified

The LL East Frisia is facing a growing water demand for the consumption groups industry, agriculture and population. Progressing climate change will lead to additional water requirements in all sectors. In order to protect the natural resource of groundwater, drinking water should only be used in specific purposes where it is absolutely necessary. Therefore, sectors are identified where drinking water can be substituted by treated process water. The B-WaterSmart pilot plant at the DMK dairy in Edeweicht is used to test and demonstrate the treatment of cow water in order to substitute drinking water.

The current situation for the dairy industry (DMK Group) is to partly reuse cow water for backwashing. As seen in Figure 15, vapor condensate (**cow water**) will be used to produce **reclaimed water for industrial reuse (C12)**. To this aim, by a combination of biological, bio-physical and membrane processes, the cow water is treated, refining the quality. In particular, a pilot plant was set up to test the improved treatment of that cow water for reuse in the water-intensive dairy sector. The treatment involves specifically the use of a combined biology-ultrafiltration-reverse osmosis through a pilot treatment train (moving bed biofilm reactor - multi layer filter - ultrafiltration - reverse osmosis - ultraviolet disinfection) to obtain a **purified grade water** that could be reused.

This circularity scope of LL East Frisia is expected to be broadened by treating alternative water resources such as the **municipal/industrial/urban wastewater to obtain more reclaimed water in a separate process (C13)** to be reused **for non-potable uses** (i.e. industrial).

Figure 15. Complete map of the circularities of LL East Frisia.

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 36 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 36. List of stakeholders identified in LL East Frisia.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category/ Sector	Circularity involved
Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband (OOWV)	Water services providers in Germany, delivering drinking water from groundwater resources to private, industrial and agricultural customers (and treating wastewater in ~50% of the area).	Water industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C12, C13
Water supply company	Water supply company	Water industry	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	-
DMK Group	Dairy industry company. Pilot plant installed at DMK Edewecht, high water demand & high cow water (vapor condensate) produced.	Food industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Food	C12
EnviroChemie	EnviroChemie supplies system solutions worldwide for all the tasks involved in industrial water treatment and the treatment of process water, circulation water, cooling water, boiler water and wastewater. Supplies technology for the pilot plant at the LL.	Engineering company	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C12
District	District of the pilot site.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	C12
Agriculture organization	Self-governing organization for agriculture.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	-
Public corporation	As a corporation under public law, it represents the interests of companies in the region.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Water, energy, resources, waste	-
IWW	IWW has a focus on interdisciplinary water research. In cooperation with institutes of the University of Duisburg-Essen, the Technical Universities TU Darmstadt and TU Dortmund, our scope ranges from fundamental research to the development of practical applications. Optimisation and support of technological piloting, project coordination, development of forecasting tools.	Research institute	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C12

The main stakeholders in LL East Frisia include the Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband (OOWV), a German water services provider responsible for delivering drinking water and treating wastewater; DMK Group, a dairy industry company hosting the pilot plant with a focus on treatment of cow water for the substitution of drinking water; EnviroChemie, an engineering company supplying technology for the pilot plant; public authorities collaborating in the project; and IWW, a research institute specialized in interdisciplinary water research. These stakeholders collectively represent internal stakeholders, value network stakeholders, value chain stakeholders and collaborators across the urban, industrial, and agricultural sectors (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Complete map of stakeholders of LL East Frisia.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Process water (cow water) to reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapour condensate (cow water).** The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential. (C12 - See Figure 17).

It needs to be highlighted that the following indicators are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities: stakeholder engagement and awareness and increased understanding.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C12) are:

- **Baseline scenario** DMK industry at OOWV area with no reclaimed water use. Only cow water is partly reused for backwashing.
- **Circular scenario** Introduction of a reclaimed water pilot treating cow water, increasing its quality to obtain a purified grade water for industrial reuse in DMK Group.
- **Scale-up scenario** Scale-up of the pilot plant at DMK for large-scale water reuse at the dairy, potential to replicate this system in other DMK plants.

Figure 17. Diagram of input and output flows for Circularity C12. Process water (cow water) to reclaimed water. Increase water reuse in the dairy industry through combined treatment of vapor condensate (cow water). The milk/whey permeate is already partly used within DMK for cooling processes or as pre-cleaning water. In addition, the extended internal use of milk/whey permeate holds potential.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C12 are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. LL East Frisia circularity (C12) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The transformation of cow water into reclaimed water plays an important role in advancing several SDGs. Firstly, **SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation** is directly addressed as this process contributes to the sustainable management and efficient use of water resources by substituting drinking water by reclaiming water and enabling industrial growth while maintaining the same demand for drinking water. Additionally, by converting cow water into reclaimed water, **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities** is supported, promoting resilient and sustainable urban environments through responsible water management practices. Furthermore, this circularity influences **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure** by demonstrating innovative approaches in water treatment within the industrial sector. Lastly, the transformation contributes to **SDG 13: Climate Action** by mitigating the environmental impact through sustainable water practices, thereby fostering resilience to climate change.

According to available data and current operational status of the pilot plant at DMK, some indicators were evaluated to monitor the circularity and expected results in the future scenario. More information regarding the CBM development will follow in Deliverable 4.4 “Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs”.

It needs to be highlighted that to ensure uniformity of the indicators, cow water from the dairy is assessed like wastewater of the other LLs. As the reclaim process of cow water and the dairy production are two different process models, the indicators only include an assessment of the cow water flow in the production and no other water flows in the dairy. Therefore, the cow water discharged into the environment ($766,000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$) and the partially recycled milk/whey condensate discharged ($350,000 \text{ m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$) are in sum equal to the TWW. The cow water from the dairy has a good water quality and can be discharged without further treatment outside of the dairy.

Water

The **Effective Cow water Treatment** (equals the indicator Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT_{eff})) for the three scenarios is 100%, reflecting the total treatment of cow water generated at the DMK plant.

For the case of the **Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses** (RWnpU), it would be interesting to find out how much drinking water is no longer used for non-potable uses outside the production process as it is replaced by reclaimed water. However, data for the water consumption for non-potable uses outside of the production process was not available as it is not included in this stage of planning.

On the other hand, **Reclaimed Water Production** (RWP) is shown in the following Table 37. The RWP increases up to 77% in the scale-up scenario, as more reclaimed water is going to be produced and reused. There is no difference between the baseline scenario and the circular scenario as the reclaimed water from the pilot plant is not returned to the production process.

Table 37. Results of the Reclaimed Water Production (RWP) in LL East Frisia for the 3 scenarios. (*in LL EF TWW equals discharged cow water)

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
$V_{\text{reclaimed}}$	$\text{m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	350,000.00	350,000.00	860,000.00
TWW*	$\text{m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00
RWP	%	31.4	31.4	77.0

Regarding **Linear Water Losses** (LWL) and **Water Storage Capacity** (WSC), they are currently not a relevant consideration, but it is advisable to assess them in the scale-up scenario once the LL has established if they are going to have any storage capacity or they are going to distribute reclaimed water through a network, respectively. This will be investigated in the long-term depending on the results of the current pilot plant.

The **Water Footprint** (WFP) of the DMK plant considers the plant to produce reclaimed water from cow water. The WFP considers groundwater consumption in the facility, the avoided impact of the use of reclaimed water, the indirect impact of the reclaimed water production (e.g. energy and chemicals consumption) and the cow water generated and discharged into the environment.

Table 38. Results of the Water Footprint (WFP) in LL East Frisia for the 3 scenarios (*in LL EF TWW equals discharged cow water)

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
WF_{DMK}	$\text{m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	-100,718.00	-7,906.91	-458,980.12
TWW*	$\text{m}^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00
WFP_{DMK}	$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$	-0.09	-0.01	-0.41

As it is seen in Table 38, the WF_{DMK} has the lowest value in the scale-up scenario thanks to the avoided consumption of groundwater of around 450,000 m^3 per year. It is planned to use this groundwater to expand production in the future. This fact results as an improvement in the WFP for the DMK plant, with a WFP of 0,41 m^3 of avoided water per 1 m^3 of discharged cow water produced. However, the WFP is an estimation, as there is still some missing data from the reclaimed water production process that could change the results (e.g. chemicals consumption data for the circular scenario is missing). The results of this indicator for the LL East Frisia could also be assessed and compared with other functional units such as annual milk production at the plant or total reclaimed water production in order to compare it with the total cow water produced.

Air

The **Carbon Footprint** (CFP) linked to the production of reclaimed water consistently shows very low values in all scenarios. This is due to the fact that the CF has a lower magnitude

order compared to the cow water produced (1,116,000 m³ year⁻¹). The CF for the DMK plant has values of 3.7, 0.4 and 18.1 kg CO₂eq year⁻¹ for the baseline, circular and scale-up scenarios, respectively. The scale-up scenario has a higher CF because of the increase in chemicals consumption for the production of reclaimed water. However, the CFP is an estimation, as there is still some missing data from the reclaimed water production process that could change the results (e.g. chemicals consumption data for the circular scenario is missing).

Energy

The **Energy Consumption** (E_{eff}) has a higher value in the circular and scale-up scenario, as can be seen in Table 39. This is because of the increase of energy demand for the production of reclaimed water. Also, there is no data available for the energy consumption for the cow water treatment in the scale-up scenario, so the energy consumption ratio in this scenario may increase.

Table 39. Results of the Energy Consumption (E_{eff}) in LL East Frisia for the 3 scenarios. (*in LL EF TWW equals discharged cow water)

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
E_{DMK}	kWh year ⁻¹	570,000.00	1,515,000.00	1,425,000.00
TWW*	m ³ year ⁻¹	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00	1,116,000.00
E_{eff}	kWh m ⁻³	0.51	1.36	1.28

Economy and business

No data is available for the **Resource Recovery Revenues** (RRR) indicator, hence it couldn't be assessed.

Transforming the LL East Frisia (dairy industry) into a more circular model through reclaimed water production has the potential to improve the **new and modified circular economy BMs put into practice** (BM_{CE}). In the baseline scenario, only 1 conventional business model existed (dairy plant). During the circular scenario of the B-WaterSmart project, 1 new circular model consisting of the reclaimed water production for industrial reuse was implemented. The scale-up scenario realizes the same CBM as the circular model in a large-scale version, therefore, no additional CBM is realized. The progress of the CBMs implementation can be seen in the following table:

Table 40. Results of the Circular Economy Business Models put into practice (BM_{CE}) in LL East Frisia for the 3 scenarios.

Parameter	Unit	Baseline scenario	Circular scenario	Scale-up scenario
BM_{c}	No	0	1	1
BM_{tot}	No	1	2	2
BM_{CE}	%	0	50	50

Green Jobs

It is planned to employ 1 full-time employee to operate the large-scale plant at the dairy. Therefore, increasing the number of **green jobs** (GJ) in the scale-up scenario. In the baseline scenario as well as the circular scenario, no employees can be directly connected to the large-scale plant. The ratio of green jobs could increase up to 100% in the scale-up scenario.

Social acceptance

The statements reflecting both positive and negative perspectives on the extent of social acceptance have been sorted into Table 41, resulting in a neutral level.

Table 41. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL East Frisia.

East Frisia	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
There is a growing acceptance of water as a valuable resource. A significant number of citizens are aware of environmental issues and climate change. These groups, which tend to be more open-minded, as well as people with technological education are more likely to accept new solutions and have a positive attitude. Acceptance of the solution is supported by the saving of drinking water resources and the associated costs, as well as greater self-sufficiency. There is a high level of willingness to cooperate, especially among citizens who have directly experienced water scarcity, people working in particularly water-intensive sectors and environmental protection organizations.	There are potential negative perceptions about the use of treated process water in the food industry that need to be addressed with maximum clarity and transparency. This requires clarity on the legal and technical requirements. The high technical effort can be seen as shifting the problem as high energy costs are expected, so the use of climate-neutral energy is important. Due to the high responsibility, health authorities/ consumer protection authorities are expected to be rather cautious. Particularly critical groups are those who are technology skeptical or uninformed, or who have a general skepticism and concern about the quality of drinking water.
SUPPORTIVE	

Stakeholder engagement

In the LL of East Frisia, 4 collaborative activities were carried out, involving the participation of 38 individuals. The overall participation showed gender balance (57% men vs. 43% women), although the last Community of Practice (CoP) deviated from this balance, with 80% male participation. Upon analyzing the questionnaire results, a relatively good level of participation was observed, resulting in a "Collaborate" rating with an average score of 3.7. On one hand, the aspect most positively evaluated by participants was the constructive

handling of differences and conflicts among participants. On the other hand, participants highlighted an area for improvement: the effectiveness of meetings in motivating participants to take actions within their own organizations.

Awareness and increased understanding

Participants in various activities completed questionnaires, leading to the attainment of a level of "Aware" for this specific indicator, with an average score of 4.0. The aspect that garnered the highest appreciation was the clarity of the presentations and speakers. Nevertheless, participants gave a lower score to both the actions formulated to enhance solutions and the conclusions at the end of the meeting, suggesting areas for potential improvement in these aspects.

Governance soundness

Based on the analysis of the governance implications of the pilot plant (D.5.5) identified by governance experts, experienced beneficiaries, competent authorities, and the CoP, a neutral level (54.17) has been established for the governance soundness indicator of LL East Frisia. Since the solution in question is exploring untrodden ground, and decision-making for water reuse in the dairy industry demands the involvement of several authorities, the main governance issues in the East Frisia context are related to principles under the Effectiveness and Efficiency dimensions.

Table 42. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL East Frisia.

B-WaterSmart Ls	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governance Soundness
LL East Frisia	25	$(25-12/36-12)*100$	54.17	Neutral

*It should be noted that further developments have taken place since the assessment of this indicator. A conference of authorities was held in December 2023 with a positive outcome.

In summary, taking into account the results of the analysis related to the indicators for the scenarios in East Frisia, it is expected that the reuse of water will increase in the dairy industry without increasing the demand of fresh water (in case of LL Eeast Frisia groundwater) in the dairy. It is planned to use this fresh water to expand production in the future. To do so, clarity on the regulatory and technical requirements is needed. Additionally, the indicator Effective Cow Water Treatment (equals WWT_{eff}) is consistently 100% in all three scenarios, reflecting the total treatment of cow water generated at the DMK plant. The footprints are very low, due to the lack of data on consumables in the reclaimed production process in some scenarios. However, the circularity of the dairy industry under study reflects significant potential, which should be enhanced with the contribution of stakeholders to data collection. Additionally, stakeholders in LL East Frisia show active engagement and gender balance.

3.3.5 Living Lab Flanders

LL Summary

Table 43. Summary of LL Flanders.

“LL Flanders requires additional data for a full assessment, with pilot evaluations still in progress. In governance and social aspects, stakeholder engagement has achieved a good score, though regulatory disparities in rainwater and stormwater management present challenges.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL Flanders

- **Objective:** Develop stormwater reuse systems to improve water availability for agriculture and enhance drinking water production resilience.
- **Circularities identified (3):**
 - Stormwater collection and treatment: Nature-based solutions combined with sand filtration to provide reclaimed water for irrigation.
 - Water retention and reuse: Buffer basins adapted to prevent flooding while storing water for agriculture.
 - Drinking water security: Use of municipal wastewater treatment effluent as an indirect source for drinking water
- **Impact across scenarios** (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):
 - Circularity prioritized: Stormwater to reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation
 - Stormwater collection: No system → Pilot-level treatment → Full-scale regional system.
 - Groundwater stress reduction: Lower irrigation dependency on groundwater.
 - Carbon footprint and energy: Pending data from pilot implementation.
 - Green jobs: Expected increase, but no concrete figures yet
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 17 stakeholders engaged; representativeness and gender-balanced..
 - Farmers support stormwater reuse, but concerns exist over treated effluent use for drinking water.
 - Regulatory gaps between rainwater, stormwater, and infiltration management hinder full implementation

Circularities identified

The LL Flanders aims to develop a regional concept for improving and monitoring water intelligence, focusing on safe water reuse and improved integration of natural water systems. The aim is to model water availability, demand and possible alternative sources, as well as to demonstrate the practical application of water reuse (Figure 19). Several local **applications of alternative water sources** are currently being studied, such as alternative water resources for drinking water production and further purification of surface water through reverse osmosis, as well as the retention and reuse of rain and stormwater for agriculture.

To achieve the objectives, on the one hand, **stormwater will be collected** from urban areas in a basin meant for flood prevention. The basin is adapted to facilitate collection while still ensuring flood prevention. The collected stormwater is treated through a sand filtration treatment. Treated water will be **reused for agriculture** purposes through subirrigation, which also contributes to the resilience of the groundwater system. On the other hand, it is expected to ensure robust drinking water production by improving the drinking water treatment to cope with off-spec raw surface water and by making **indirect use of the municipal WWTP effluent for drinking water production**. For this purpose, a pre-treatment and further membrane treatment is needed to **increase drinking water production**. It is necessary to clarify that the stormwater management circularity is not related to the drinking water production.

Figure 19. Complete map of the circularities of LL Flanders.

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 44 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 44. List of stakeholders identified in LL Flanders.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (PSKW)	Non-profit organization, leading knowledge and innovation center for vegetable cultivation focussing on practical and applied research.	Research institute	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Resources	C14
City of Mechelen	Municipality of the city of Mechelen	Public authority	Partner	Value Network Stakeholders	All the above	C14
Westkustpolder	A public authority for local water management active in the territory of Alveringem, Poperinge, Vleteren, Lo-Reninge, Ieper, Langemark-Poelkapelle, Houthulst & Diksmuide. They manage the local waterway, taking care of the locks, weirs and pumping stations.	Public authority	Observer	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C15,C16
Zuidijzerpolder	A public authority for local water management active in the territory of De Panne, Koksijde, Nieuwpoort, Veurne, Diksmuide, Alveringem & Lo-Reninge. They manage the local waterway, taking care of the locks, weirs and pumping stations.	Public authority	Observer	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C15,C16
Natuurpunt	An independent volunteer association with more than 130,000 members, protecting vulnerable and endangered nature in Flanders. They are specifically aiming for a nature-inclusive Flanders.	NGOs, associations	Observer	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C15,C16
Vito	An independent Flemish research organization that provides scientific advice and technological innovations that facilitate the transition to a sustainable society (in the areas of water, energy, chemistry, materials, health, land use, and more).	Research institute	Partner	Internal Stakeholders	All the above	C14

Table 44. List of stakeholders identified in LL Flanders. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
VLAQWA	Independent intermediary operating as a knowledge center for the integral water cycle. They initiate, coordinate and facilitate cooperation, experience and knowledge exchange, and knowledge building between businesses, researchers and authorities in their search for sustainable and innovative solutions to water problems and ways to implement them.	Research institute	Partner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C14
Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij	Regulatory body, environment agency of the region. Responsible for regulation and permitting of environmental issues including (waste) water. They are also responsible for reporting the state of the environment towards the EU.	Public authority	Collaborator	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C14
Provincie Antwerpen	Northernmost province both of the Flemish Region, and of Belgium	Public authority	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	All the above	C14
Municipality of Diksmuide	Municipality of the city of Diksmuide.	Public authority	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	All the above	C15, C16
Aqua Flanders	The federation of Flemish water companies and sewer managers. They promote the interests of their members with local, regional, federal and European governments and stakeholders. AquaFlanders cooperates on a streamlined and modern water management. They also want to inform and raise awareness about sustainable water usage in Flanders.	NGOs, associations	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	Waste	C15
Aquafin	Experts in wastewater collection and treatment, they are responsible for the financing, operation and expansion of the wastewater treatment infrastructure in Flanders. They collect wastewater from the Flemish municipalities and treat it before it is returned to nature. They also help municipalities deal with stormwater differently, by making more space for it and integrating it into public areas.	Water industry	Partner	Internal Stakeholders	Waste	C14, C15

Table 44. List of stakeholders identified in LL Flanders. (Continued)

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Pidpa	In circularity C14, Pidpa is involved as the sewerage manager of the city of Mechelen. Separate from this, Pidpa serves consumers in Belgium, managing the public water distribution network (water intended for human consumption).The Company distributes drinking water, as well as offers wastewater management, construction and operation of pumping stations, new connections, and billing facilities.	Water industry	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Water	C14, C16
De Watergroep	Public (municipality owned) company, largest drinking water company in Flanders.	Water industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Water	C15, C16
De Vlaamse Waterweg	Manages and exploits the waterways network that contributes to the economy, prosperity and quality of life in Flanders.They strengthen transport via inland shipping, ensure water management and increase the attractiveness of the waterways for recreation, tourism and nature experience.	Public authority	Observer	Value Network Stakeholders	Water	C15, C16
Boerenbond	Professional organization for every agricultural entrepreneur in Flanders and East Belgium. With our local and regional board members and a strong team of experts, we bring our 16,000 members together to work – in dialogue with society – for a robust and sustainable agricultural and horticultural sector with a future.	Agricultural company, association and end-user	Follower	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C14
Flanders' FOOD	Innovation platform for the Flemish agri-food industry. Together with their members – businesses, research institutes, organizations and federations – they make up the agri-food spearhead cluster, the network for innovation in the agri-food industry. They support food companies in initiating, developing and implementing innovations in food products, production systems and new business concepts.	Innovation platform	Follower	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C14

In Living Lab Flanders, a dynamic group of stakeholders actively participates in the transformative initiative of converting stormwater into reclaimed water for agricultural use and maximizing the production of drinking water, emphasizing circular practices. Several key players have direct involvement in these practices. Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (PSKW) is a non-profit organization and research institute dedicated to the circular use of resources, particularly in the realm of agriculture. Moreover, the City of Mechelen, as a municipal authority, plays a central role in the circular conversion of stormwater. Also Vito, an independent Flemish research organization, provides scientific advice and technological innovations.

In the case of circular efforts in environmental regulation, particularly in the domain of water, it is the Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij, a regulatory body and environmental agency that is engaged. Aquafin uses its expertise in wastewater collection and treatment to contribute to extending financing, operating, and expanding wastewater treatment infrastructure. In addition, Pidpa contributes to circularity in water management within the LL and De Watergroep, as the largest drinking water company in Flanders, serving as a partner and internal stakeholder which focuses on circularity related to effluent reuse for drinking water supply.

The collaborative efforts of these diverse stakeholders collectively contribute to the circular transformation of stormwater into reclaimed water and the effluent reuse for drinking water supply, emphasizing the importance of a multi-stakeholder approach for sustainable water management and environmental conservation.

As seen in Figure 20, stakeholders are well-represented in various circularity environments such as city, industry, agriculture, and ecosystem. There are not many industries involved as for now water reuse especially in the industrial sector has still needs to be sufficiently explored.

Figure 20. Complete map of stakeholders of LL Flanders.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Stormwater to reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation** (C14 - See Figure 21).

It needs to be highlighted that some of the indicators from the categories Economy and Business (i.e. Circular economy business Models in practice), Green Jobs and Social are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C14) are:

- **Baseline scenario** No stormwater collection system implemented. Stormwater directly flows to the local watercourse, accidentally causing floods in downstream urban areas. The groundwater system is under pressure through the presence of drainage systems and groundwater abstraction for irrigation needs.
- **Circular scenario** Introduction of a stormwater collection system combining a buffering and collection function and treatment based on a nature-based solution. Pilot plant to treat the stormwater with sand filtration. Agricultural water reuse through subirrigation by adapting existing drainage systems.
- **Scale-up scenario** Replicate and scale-up the stormwater collection and treatment systems.

Figure 21. Diagram of input and output flows for circularity C14. Stormwater to reclaimed water. Stormwater reuse for irrigation.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C14 are shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. LL Flanders circularity (C14) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This initiative contributes to **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities** by creating sustainable urban spaces, increasing resilience to climate change and improving inclusive public environments. **SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation** is addressed through water use optimization and improved water quality achieved by reclaiming stormwater. The project also contributes with **SDG 13: Climate Action** by mitigating climate change impacts through efficient stormwater management and adapting to changing climate patterns by working on flood prevention and groundwater replenishment in the same application. In terms of **SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure**, the LL promotes innovation in water management, promoting sustainable infrastructure development and showcasing a model for global application of circular practices in stormwater management for agricultural practices.

According to available data and current operational status of the project, some indicators were assessed to monitor the circularity and expected results in the future scenario. More information regarding the CBM development will follow in Deliverable 4.4 “Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs”.

Indicators:

The following indicators are those that should be considered for LL Flanders:

- Water: Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT_{eff}) Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU), Reclaimed Water Production (RWP), Linear Water Losses (LWL), Water Storage Capacity (WSC), Water Footprint (WFP).
- Air: Carbon Footprint (CFP).
- Energy: Energy Consumption (E_{eff}).
- Economy and business: , Circular Economy Business Models in Practice (BM_{CE}).
- Green Jobs (GJ).

However, they could not be evaluated yet as the necessary data from the pilot to make the relevant calculations is not yet available due to the fact that the pilot is not yet completed. As elaborated in D2.17 “Second intermediate synthesized report of technology progress and

state of play across all the LLs“, the technology showcasing stormwater reuse for agriculture consists of several subparts (e.g. stormwater management tool to adapt buffer basin to have a dual buffer - collection function, transformation from a drainage to a subirrigation system and assessing its agricultural effects, providing water treatment, controlling subirrigation, etc.). All these subparts are now being integrated during the demo and the necessary data will only be present once all subparts have been integrated for a sufficiently long time, which will be the case in the coming months.

Social acceptance

The phrases associated with more positive and negative stances regarding the level of social acceptance have been categorized in Table 45, yielding a neutral level.

Table 45. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL Flanders.

Flanders	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
Based on a 2022 survey, the findings show a variable degree of acceptability depending on the type of water and use: the potential use of effluents as drinking water is generally rejected whereas, the use of rainwater for agriculture is accepted. Indeed, decision makers are in favor of reusing effluents for agriculture and irrigation in sports fields. There is a growing understanding of solutions. With regard to rainwater, there is also acceptance because it impacts on farmers who are often seen as a sector that always has to make more efforts than others. On top of that, it is believed that accepting rainwater could attract businesses.	Low awareness of water treatment costs can act as an obstacle to the implementation of treatment solutions. Initiatives with citizen participation are difficult to implement, due to lack of interest. Due to the quality, the reuse of effluents for agriculture is considered difficult. Intense contact between water and crops for human consumption could raise concerns about food safety, taste and quality. Companies avoid sharing water reuse in the media. Breweries also avoid the use of reused water in processes where there could be potential contact with their product. According to a 2022 study, despite technological development, consumer resistance remains.
NEUTRAL	

Stakeholder engagement

In Living Lab Flanders, 3 collaborative activities were conducted, engaging the participation of 39 individuals. The overall participation exhibited gender balance (55% men vs. 40% women). Upon scrutinizing the evaluation survey results, a praiseworthy level of participation emerged, resulting in a "Collaborative" status with an average score of 4.3. On one hand, the aspect most positively assessed by participants was the perception that they could express themselves spontaneously and without filters during meetings. On the other hand,

participants identified an area for improvement: the inclusion of all ideas and perspectives during the discussion.

Awareness and increased understanding

Based on the evaluation survey filled out by participants in the various activities, a level of "Aware" was reached for this specific indicator, obtaining an average score of 4.2. The aspect that received the highest appreciation was the clarity of the presentations and speakers. However, participants assigned low scores to both the conclusions of the meeting and the better understanding of the stakeholders' perspective, indicating areas for potential improvement in these aspects.

Governance soundness

Based on the analysis of LL Flanders self-assessment (D.5.5), the governance assessment focuses only on the governance implications of stormwater reuse for agriculture. The final score obtained in this case is 50, assigning a neutral level to LL Flanders. The principles with lower scores, thus significantly blocking the implementation of the solution, are the lack of policy coherence, and the lack of clarity and disparities between the regulation of rainwater, stormwater, and infiltration methods.

Table 46. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL Flanders.

B-WaterSmart LLs	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governance Soundness
LL Flanders	16	$(16-8/24-8)*100$	50	Neutral

In the case of Flanders, limited information has been derived. For this reason, additional information needs to be collected for a complete assessment. In addition, the evaluation of the pilots is still ongoing, and their progress should also be considered when interpreting the results. All the indicators (water, air, green jobs, etc.) need to be calculated and evaluated in order to make an appropriate assessment. Once more complete information is available, LL Flanders will review this to ensure a more accurate and technical assessment of the different scenarios.

In the governance and social axis, LL Flanders has achieved a good score in all three dimensions of stakeholder engagement. Nevertheless, the lack of clarity and disparities in the regulation of rainwater, stormwater, and infiltration methods pose challenges to the overall governance effectiveness.

3.3.6 Living Lab Bodø

LL Summary

Table 47. Summary of LL Bodø.

“LL Bodø requires additional data for a complete assessment. Then, it is suggested to be reviewed again once all the information is available, ensuring a more accurate assessment of the different scenarios. Governance and stakeholder engagement scored well, but public awareness on water consumption and the costs of nature-based solutions needs improvement.”

Key results of circularity assessment – LL Bodø

- **Objective:** Assess waste-to-energy solutions for Bodø and Salten through biogas production from sludge and organic waste.
- **Circularities identified** (1 with 4 alternatives to address it):
 - Co-digestion of sludge and organic waste to produce biogas, compost, biopellets, and biochar. Four technology pathways assessed:
 - Anaerobic digestion + composting (biogas & compost).
 - Anaerobic digestion + pelletizing (biogas & biopellets).
 - Anaerobic digestion + pyrolysis (biogas & biochar).
 - UASB reactor + pyrolysis (biogas & biochar)
- **Impact across scenarios** (Baseline → Circular → Scale-up):
 - Energy production from biogas: Feasibility study ongoing.
 - Carbon footprint reduction: Data pending from implementation.
 - Use of recovered materials: Compost and biochar for agriculture & soil conditioning.
 - Green jobs: Potential increase, but not quantified
- **Stakeholder & Governance:**
 - 9 stakeholders engaged; representativeness and gender-balanced..
 - Social support for energy recovery, with varying levels of acceptance for water conservation solutions.
 - Strong governance performance, but policy coordination challenges remain.

Circularities identified

The main objective in the case of LL Bodø is to analyze different alternatives of transforming **waste into energy** in a waste management facility (Figure 23).

The following Table 48 shows the alternatives (Alt.) selected based on a desk study according to their feasibility in LL Bodø:

Table 48. Summary of alternatives to be assessed in LL Bodø.

Alt.	Technology	Input					Output	Possible marketed output
		Bodø sludge	Salten sludge	Food waste	Garden waste	Fish sludge		
Alt.1	THP + AD + Composting	YES	YES	YES	YES, in composting	YES	biogas , compost	Heat, electricity, compost
Alt.2	THP + AD + Pelletizing	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	biogas , biopellet	Heat, electricity, biopellets
Alt.3	THP + AD + Pyrolysis	YES	YES	YES	YES, in pyrolysis	YES	biogas , biochar	Heat, electricity, biochar
Alt.4	THP + Pyrolysis + UASB	YES	YES	YES	YES, in pyrolysis	YES	biogas , biochar	Heat, electricity, biochar

In this way, the first alternative (Alt. 1) consists in the **co-digestion of sludge and organic waste** (i.e. food waste and fish sludge) from the cities of Bodø and Salten in Norway, with the objective of producing **compost** and **biogas**. For this, a thermal hydrolysis process (THP) would be implemented, followed by anaerobic digestion (AD) and composting. For the composting process garden waste would be included. The same procedure occurs in the second case (Alt. 2), with the difference that **biopellets** are generated in order of compost, through a process of **pelletizing**.

The third alternative (Alt. 3) involves the co-digestion of sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten too, generating biosolids (treated digestate) and garden waste mixed for **biochar production**. The process includes THP, AD and pyrolysis. The fourth pathway (ALT. 4) to be explored is the same as the previous one, but using an Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) instead of the AD. It is used for liquid fraction from sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten treatment. Biosolids (solid fraction) and garden waste will be also mixed for **biochar production**.

Examining all these alternatives, it is intended to increase the **production of energy** through biogas, serving not only for this process, but also to distribute electricity and heat to the public network. By-products obtained such as compost and biopellets could be used in the agriculture sector to improve the land by adding nutrients or as a soil conditioner.

Figure 23. Complete map of the circularities of LL Bodø.

Stakeholders identified

The following Table 49 shows the different stakeholders identified in the LL and its collaboration in the circularities identified.

Table 49. List of stakeholders identified in LL Bodø.

Stakeholder	Description	Entity type	Role	Group	Category / Sector	Circularity involved
Bodø municipality	Operator of the water network. Sludge producer.	Water industry	Partner - LL owner	Internal Stakeholders	Resources	C17
AVINOR	Customer.	End-user	Observer	Value Chain Stakeholders	Energy	C17
Bodø Energi Varme AS	Customer.	End-user	Collaborator	Value Chain Stakeholders	Energy	C17
IRIS	Intermunicipal waste company. Compost of sewage sludge. Participation in the desk study of co-digestion.	Representatives of other sectors	Core co-creator	Internal Stakeholders	Resources	C17
Fish farms	Producer of fish sludge which may be supplemented for biogas production.	Agriculture company	Potential stakeholder. Not contacted yet in CoP.	Value Chain Stakeholders	Resources	C17
Salten municipalities	The municipalities of Gildeskål, Bodø, Beiarn, Saltdal, Fauske, Sørfold, Steigen, and Hamarøy. Sludge producer.	Public authority	Potential stakeholder. Not contacted yet in CoP.	Internal Stakeholders	Resources	C17
Statsforvalteren i Nordland	The state administrator in Nordland.	Public authority	Potential stakeholder. Not contacted yet in CoP.	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C17
Nordlands Fylkeskommune	Nordland County Municipality.	Public authority	Potential stakeholder. Not contacted yet in CoP.	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C17
Mattilsynet	Norwegian Food Safety Authority.	Public authority	Potential stakeholder. Not contacted yet in CoP.	Value Network Stakeholders	Resources	C17

In the LL Bodø, some stakeholders stand out with several functions such as the Bodø Municipality, which operates the water network and produces sludge within the water industry. Positioned as internal stakeholders, they hold roles as a partner and local level owner, focusing on resource management. In addition, AVINOR, an external stakeholder, serves as a customer and end-user observer in the energy sector's value chain stakeholders, contributing insights related to circularity practices. Also it is very important Bodø Energi Varme AS, another energy-centric stakeholder, which collaborates as a customer and end-user. The waste management company IRIS plays a core co-creator role, contributing expertise in composting sewage sludge and resource management. Potential stakeholders are Fish Farms too, which have not been contacted yet, but identified as valuable contributors in the resources sector for their fish sludge with biogas production potential. Similarly, Salten Municipalities, covers multiple public authorities, contributing to circularity goals.

As seen in Figure 24, stakeholders are well-represented in various circularity environments such as city, industry, agriculture and port. However, it is important to note that there is currently a gap in stakeholder representation within the ecosystem environment.

Figure 24. Complete map of stakeholders of LL Bodø.

Circularity assessment

The assessment focuses on the circularity prioritized: **Waste to energy (desk study). Increase of energy production through biogas** (C17 - See Figure 25).

It needs to be highlighted that some of the indicators from the categories Economy and Business (i.e. Circular economy business Models in practice), Green Jobs and Social are evaluated considering the whole LL and all the circularities.

The scenarios that are considered for the prioritized circularity (C17) are:

- **Baseline scenario** Composting and landfill.
- **Alternative 1** Co-digestion of sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten; compost production.
- **Alternative 2** Co-digestion of sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten; biopellets production
- **Alternative 3** Co-digestion of sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten; biosolids (treated digestate) and garden waste mixed for biochar production.
- **Alternative 4** UASB for liquid fraction from sludge and organic waste from Bodø and Salten treatment; biosolids (solid fraction) and garden waste mixed for biochar production.

Figure 25. Diagram of input and output flows for circularity C17. Waste to energy. Increase of energy production through biogas.

The SDGs that have been prioritized and most contribute to the circularity C1 are shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26. LL Bodø circularity (C17) and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The energy production through biogas can contribute to **SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy** and the co-digestion process using local organic waste from Bodø and Salten can also promote new business opportunities in the municipalities (**SDG 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure**). Furthermore, introducing circularities that involve urban infrastructure and the use of waste as resources with the objective of producing green energy for urban areas can foster **SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities** and **SDG 13: Climate Action**. The same for **SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production**, since the source of the energy produced has to be sustainable.

According to available data and current desk study level, some indicators were evaluated to monitor the circularity and expected results in the future scenario. More information regarding the CBM development will follow in Deliverable 4.4 “Guidelines to improve new Business models at Living Labs”.

Indicators:

The following indicators are those that should be considered for LL Bodø:

- Water: Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT_{eff}), Water Footprint (WFP).
- Air: Carbon Footprint (CFP).
- Waste: Water-related materials’ Recovery (WR), Fertilizer Production Avoided (FPA).
- Energy: Energy Consumption (E_{eff}), Energy Production (EP).
- Economy and business: Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR), Circular Economy Business Models in Practice (BM_{CE}).
- Green Jobs (GJ).

However, they could not yet be assessed as the necessary data from the desk study is not yet available to make the relevant calculations.

As the scope of LL Bodø is a desk study, D4.3 is tied to T2.2.2. The previous feasibility study found that biogas was infeasible due to the quantities of sludge produced in Bodø, the study now investigates a shared biogas reactor between the Salten regional area. Much of the data being requested in D4.3 will be used in T2.2.2, however this data will be accumulated and requested later.

Social acceptance

The phrases associated with more positive and negative stances regarding the level of social acceptance have been categorized in Table 50, yielding a bad level. Therefore, the resistant level has been assigned to the LL.

Table 50. Results of the social acceptance assessment in LL Bodø.

Bodø	
<i>Positive</i>	<i>Negative</i>
There is a high level of trust towards the municipality and institutions. This result is in line with other studies.	There is concern about the cost of the nature-based solution. In addition to that, there is a lack of public awareness about water consumption, due to its presence in the territory. According to a survey, less than half of the population believes that solutions to reduce water consumption are an important environmental measure (and less than 17% think that reducing consumption at home is useful).
RESISTANT	

Stakeholder engagement

In the LL of Bodø, 5 collaborative activities were conducted, involving the participation of 115 individuals. Overall participation was balanced by gender. Upon analyzing the questionnaire results, a good level of participation was observed, resulting in a "Collaborative" level with an average score of 4.3. On one hand, the aspect most positively evaluated by participants was the perception that they could express themselves spontaneously and without filters during meetings. On the other hand, participants highlighted an area for improvement: the inclusion of all ideas and perspectives during the discussion.

Awareness and increased understanding

According to the questionnaires completed by participants in various activities, a level of "Aware" was achieved for this specific indicator, with an average score of 4.2. The aspect most appreciated was the clarity of the presentations and speakers, while a lower score was assigned to the clear actions formulated to enhance solutions.

Governance soundness

According to the governance assessment of BWS Living Labs, the Bodø LL has attained the highest final score (75) for the governance soundness indicator. Although some challenges persist and vary across the implemented solutions (especially under the Effectiveness and Efficiency dimensions), all the OECD principles evaluated in the Bodø context have obtained a relatively high total score, which results in a governance which promotes the water smart solutions.

Table 51. Results of the governance soundness assessment in LL Bodø.

B-WaterSmart LLS	Overall Score*	Equation	Final score (%)	Governanc e Soundness
LL Bodø	30	$(30-12/36-12)*100$	75	Promoter

In conclusion, LL Bodø still lacks information that needs to be collected and estimated for a complete assessment. It is needed that all the indicators (water, air, green jobs, etc.) could be calculated and evaluated. Then, it is suggested to be reviewed again by the LL once complete information is available, thus ensuring a more accurate and technical assessment of the different scenarios.

In the governance and social aspects, LL Bodø has achieved a commendable score in all three dimensions of stakeholder engagement, which is reflected in the overall governance soundness. However, there is a need to raise public awareness about water consumption and to reassure the population regarding the costs of the nature-based solutions.

4 EU taxonomy in the circularity assessment of the Living Labs

4.1 The EU Taxonomy introduction

The EU Taxonomy is a classification system categorizing sustainable economic activities. It offers guidance to stakeholders, investors, companies, and policymakers on identifying environmentally responsible practices. Its primary aim is to advise on which economic activities align with greater environmental sustainability, allowing for informed decision-making in investment allocation. The overarching objective is to prioritize and direct investments towards sustainable projects, facilitating the transition of businesses toward a more circular and climate-friendly economy. This strategic approach will help accomplish the European Commission's climate and energy targets for 2030 but also contribute to the realization of the broader objectives outlined in the European Green Deal for 2050.

The climate change mitigation and climate change adaptation objectives were legally binding as of January 2022. The remaining objectives are legally binding by January 2023. Especially the fourth objective "Transition to a circular economy" serves as a guideline to follow for each activity in each LL.

4.2 Relevance for B-WaterSmart

The EU Taxonomy emerges as an essential element within the context of B-WaterSmart. First of all, water is a substantial part of the taxonomy, and the taxonomy delineates what constitutes a sustainable activity and aims at directing financial investments into businesses with taxonomy-aligned economic activities. The taxonomy criteria will serve as guidelines for all businesses in the coming years and are therefore of high relevance given the multifaceted involvement of various businesses in the project's LLs. The businesses in B-WaterSmart are compelled to align their activities with the Taxonomy criteria if they wish to be eligible for external funding for further investments and development under the EU funding regimes. The Taxonomy's relevance lies in providing a common understanding of what is to be considered a sustainable economic activity, hence it establishes a bottom line for the project's sustainable activities.

As the criteria evolve over time, B-WaterSmart can proactively establish new indicators based on updated Taxonomy criteria, ensuring continued alignment with evolving sustainability standards. The "Do no significant harm"-criteria have not been considered as of now for this work, however, it can be added later on. More detailed descriptions of the living labs make it easier to pick out relevant taxonomy activities and would be a prerequisite for the criteria alignment. Moreover, the Taxonomy's detailed criteria facilitate a more nuanced understanding of the relevance of specific activities within the LLs.

4.3 Recap from Task 4.2 “Circular Economy value chains”

In the previous deliverable D4.2, a full list of CE indicators was defined to measure and improve circularity in the LLs. The list consisted of 28 indicators within eight categories: economy and business, water, air, waste, energy, environment, society, and green jobs.

Based on these indicators, which have also been updated to the ones present in this deliverable D4.3, four of the taxonomy contribution criteria were identified as relevant and adapted preliminary to B-WaterSmart's CE list of indicators, as shown in Table 52. These taxonomy criteria originate from the two first climate change objectives (climate change mitigation and climate change adaptation), as their technical criterion has been published and are legally binding. After an introductory revision, four criteria were immediately linked to the project due to their thematic similarity, two within the category water and two within the category energy. These criteria are dynamic and can undergo development, and relevant taxonomy criteria are not exclusively limited to these four.

Table 52. EU Taxonomy contribution criteria already adapted to the B-WaterSmart CE list of indicators.

Category	Description	Unit	Taxonomy contribution criteria	Indicator for B-WaterSmart
Water	Annual percentage of rainwater that is retained in a defined area	%	<p><i>"One of the following impact indicators will be declared and calculated in the design of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. The percentage of a defined area, e.g. a residential or commercial area, where rainwater is not directly drained but retained within the area site.</i> <i>2. The estimated annual percentage of rainwater that is retained in a defined area."</i> 	8 Water Storage Capacity (WSC)
	Phosphorus recovery from wastewater	%	<p><i>"For the processes integrated at the WWTP (mainly Struvite– magnesium ammonium phosphate, $H_4MgPO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$), P recovery processes will recover at least 10% of the incoming P load."</i></p>	11 Water-related materials' Recovery (WR)
Energy	Net energy consumption of a wastewater treatment plant	kWh p.e. ⁻¹ (kilowatt hour/ population equivalent)	<p><i>"The net energy consumption of the wastewater treatment plant equals to or is lower than:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. 35 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity below 10,000 p.e.;</i> <i>2. 25 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity between 10,000 and 100,000 p.e.;</i> <i>3. 20 kWh per population equivalent (p.e.) per annum for treatment plant capacity above 100,000 p.e."</i> 	13 Energy consumption (Eeff)
	Energy consumption per water produced	kWh m ⁻³ produced water	<p><i>"The net average energy consumption for abstraction and treatment equals to or is lower than 0.5 kWh per cubic meter produced water supply."</i></p>	

The connection between circularities selected for the different LLs and the taxonomy criteria is outlined in section 4.4 below.

4.4 Development of new business models using the EU Taxonomy

Linking EU taxonomy criteria to the circularities in the LLs

In B-WaterSmart, six circularities have been identified in relation to the LLs. The circularities are C1) waste to energy, C2) wastewater to reclaimed water, C3) wastewater to raw materials, C4) waste to raw materials, C5) wastewater to energy, and C6) wastewater to hydrogen and oxygen. The circularities represent innovations for new BMs within the LLs. It was therefore relevant to look at how the taxonomy criteria can be linked to the circularities in the LLs, so that new BMs can be formed based on what is considered sustainable economic activities.

Eight taxonomy criteria were identified as relevant for the circularities within the LLs. Linking circularities within the LLs and relevant taxonomy criteria was done on a preliminary level based solely on the overview description and visualization of each LL. The Taxonomy Navigator and the Technical Screening Criteria (Platform on Sustainable Finance, 2022) was used to find the preliminary relevant criteria for each LL (Table 53).

Table 53. Identified Taxonomy criteria relevant for B-WaterSmart LLs. *From technical screening criteria March 2022.

Sector	Activity	Significant taxonomy criteria
Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation	Anaerobic digestion of bio-waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of biogas in other sectors - Source segregated and collected separately - Digestate as fertilizer or soil improver
Sewerage	Production of alternative water resources*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reclaimed water for reuse - Gray water segregated at source and reused
Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation	Construction, extension and operation of wastewater collection and treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Net energy consumption criteria of wastewater treatment plants - Assessment of direct GHG emissions from construction, extension and/or treatment plants
Water supply	Water supply*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metering at consumer level for existing water supply systems - Leakage level lower than 2.0 for new or extended water systems - Leakage level reduction requirements for renewal of existing water supply systems

Table 53. Identified Taxonomy criteria relevant for B-WaterSmart LLs. *From technical screening criteria March 2022. (Continued)

Sector	Activity	Significant taxonomy criteria
Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation	Material recovery from non-hazardous waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conversion into secondary materials substituting virgin materials in production processes
Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation	Anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Minimize methane leakage at facility - Use of biogas in other sectors
Sewerage	Urban wastewater treatment*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compliance with Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive - Anaerobic digestion to stabilize sludge
Energy	Cogeneration of heat/cool and power from bioenergy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Min. 80% reduction of GHG by use of biomass in cogeneration installations - Harvest of agricultural and forest biomass not affecting e.g. land use - Installation size relevance for applicability

The eight taxonomy criteria are linked with the six LLs and their circular activity as shown in Figure 27 below.

Taxonomy activity / LL	Alicante	Lisbon	Venice	Flanders	East Frisia	Bodø
(1) Anaerobic digestion of bio-waste	C1					
(2) Production of alternative water resources	C2	C1, C2	C1	C1, C2, C3	C2*	C1
(3) Construction, extension and operation of wastewater collection and treatment	C2	C1, C2	C1	C2, C3		C1
(4) Water supply	C2	C2	C1	C2, C3	C2*	
(5) Material recovery from non-hazardous waste	C4					
(6) Anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge			C2, C3			C1
(7) Urban wastewater treatment				C1		
(8) Cogeneration of heat/cool and power from bioenergy	C1					C1

*In the case of LL EF, the circularity is from cow water to reclaimed water, but as the cow water would otherwise be discharged, it is considered equivalent in this context.

Figure 27. Summary of taxonomy criteria relevant for the various LLs (Cx= 'circularity no. x')

How can this be useful going forward?

Going forward in the project, this overview of connections between LL circularities and taxonomy criteria creates an important strategic starting point for business model development. The EU Taxonomy is a dynamic framework with forthcoming criteria updates, and all firms will eventually be affected by these criteria. It is useful for the project to conduct a more detailed mapping of the activities within the circularities of each LL, because it will make it easier to select specific relevant taxonomy criteria which affects the LL's economic activities. In turn, new indicators can be established based on these updated criteria. The criteria for "Do no significant harm", which is a part of the criteria, have not been considered in this work so far, but can be added later.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the current linear economic model is no longer feasible, requiring a substantial change in the way societies generate and use resources. Consequently, a transition to a circular economy (CE) model that emphasizes waste reduction and optimal use of all resources becomes imperative. It is therefore necessary to assess circularity through a set of CE indicators that not only measure and improve circular practices, but also drive the adoption of a more sustainable cultural approach.

This deliverable D4.3 “Guidelines of circular economy models of each Living Lab” has provided information on the application of circular practices and their impact. From the detailed mapping of circularities within the Living Labs (LLs) to the selection of various indicators covering environmental, governance, economic and social factors. These indicators were updated according to the new needs of the LLs and according to the water-energy-resources nexus and the objectives of the B-WaterSmart project. The evaluation phase, which prioritizes circularities and assesses the robustness of governance, provides a structured view of the project dynamics and the results, presented in various categories, show the influence of different scenarios and circularities on the environment and local context. The evaluation procedure focused on the monitoring of the stakeholders involved, as well as on the collection of data results. The Alicante case stands out with six circularities identified, one of which is going to be scale-up in the coming months thanks to the valuable participation of all the LL partners and stakeholders involved. Bodø, on the other hand, is still in the process of evaluating different alternatives in order to implement the most effective one to achieve the planned goals of its strategic agenda.

Regarding the social dimension of the circularities, participatory processes have successfully generated significant impacts in the development of circular water solutions. In particular, the acceptance, increased awareness and knowledge of the community towards the circular solutions proposed by each LL. However, there is an acknowledgment of the lack of comparative results with other projects or initiatives, as well as the absence of unified indicators and strategies at the measurement level. The absence of an initial baseline has also been a challenge, underscoring the need to establish benchmarks for future evaluations and comparisons. This is why the relevance of the Water-Smartness assessment framework (WP6) is highlighted as a valuable tool for assessing and improving the performance of the implementation of circular solutions in different territories.

The analysis of the governance assessment reveals that the major challenges in territorial governance towards circular and innovative solutions are those related to policy coherence, and regulatory framework, which shall be addressed together with financing support to ensure an effective adoption of water-smart tools and technologies. Despite technological advancements, regulatory barriers persist, emphasizing the importance of an efficient and cohesive governance structure at all levels to address the water-energy-resources nexus that often transcend regulatory boundaries.

These outcomes contribute significantly to the development of the B-WaterSmart water-smartness assessment framework. The aim is to utilize the indicators to assess circular opportunities in all 6 LL and scale them to a larger level, analyzing their technical and environmental feasibility. This approach will facilitate an analysis of the LL performance and the implementation of diverse strategies to enhance their sustainability.

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Appendix A – List of circular economy indicators updated

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs.

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement	Unit
Water	1 Effective Wastewater Treatment (WWT _{eff})	Share of generated wastewater that is treated in wastewater treatment facilities complying with legal requirements.	$WWT_{eff} = \frac{V_{Treatment}}{WW} \times 100$	V _{treatment} (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of treated wastewater complying with legal requirements; WW (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of wastewater generated in the area/city. %
	2 Reclaimed Water in non-potable Uses (RWnpU)	Volume of reclaimed water used over the total water used for non-potable uses.	$RWnpU = \frac{RW}{npW} \times 100$	RW (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of reclaimed water used for different scopes (e.g. irrigation, street cleaning); npW (m ³ year ⁻¹): total volume of water used for non-potable uses, from all sources, including reclaimed water. “Used” may be “supplied” or “consumed”, but must be consistent in RW and npW. %
	3 Reclaimed Water Production (RWP)	Volume of reclaimed water produced (for own use or transfer to third parties) over the volume of treated wastewater or water from other non-conventional sources (e.g. stormwater).	$RWP = \frac{V_{reclaimed}}{TWW} \times 100$	V _{reclaimed} (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of reclaimed water produced in a reclamation facility under the responsibility of the utility, and which is transferred to other entities for use or for its own uses (exclude the recirculation or recycling of water, when it occurs in a closed circuit within one or more processes); TWW (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of wastewater treated, used for wastewater systems. %

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs. (Continued)

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement	Unit		
Water	4	Linear Water Losses (LWL)	Ratio of the volume of yearly water losses and the total length of the supply and/or distribution pipes of the utility for the assessment year.	$LWL = \frac{V_{loss}}{L_{net}}$	V_{loss} ($m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$): annual water losses; L_{net} (km): total length of the supply and distribution pipelines, excluding the user branches (or connection pipelines), at the assessment date of the assessment year.	$m^3 \text{ year}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$
	5	Water Storage Capacity (WSC)	Ratio between the total volume of storage (e.g. tanks for water supply, water storage from non-conventional sources such as rain harvesting systems, reclaimed water storage) and the average flow provided or demanded to the considered system (demands associated to distribution systems, rain harvesting systems, treatment plants, etc.).	$WSC = \frac{V_t}{Q_s}$	V_t (m^3): total operational volume of storage capacity; Q_s ($m^3 \text{ day}^{-1}$): yearly average flow entering or being demanded to the system.	days
	6	Water Footprint (WFP)	Water footprint associated with direct and indirect use of water for the consumption of $1m^3$ of drinking water and/or the treatment of $1m^3$ of wastewater. WFP is an indicator of direct and indirect freshwater resources appropriation. Directly used water is the amount used in the production/treatment, while indirect is the amount used in producing products, processes, systems, etc. that is used in the production/treatment of the product. It follows the Water Footprint Network (WFN) methodology.	$WFP_{dw} = \frac{WF_{dw}}{DWP}$ $WFP_{ww} = \frac{WF_{ww}}{TWW}$	WFP_{dw} ($m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$): water footprint in the drinking water system and WFP_{ww} ($m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$): water footprint in the wastewater system; DWP ($m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$): annual drinking water production; used for drinking water systems and TWW ($m^3 \text{ year}^{-1}$): volume of wastewater treated; used for wastewater systems.	$m^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs. (Continued)

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement	Unit
Air	7 Carbon Footprint (CFP)	Carbon footprint that is emitted directly and indirectly for the consumption of 1 m ³ of drinking water and/or treatment of 1 m ³ of wastewater.	$CFP_{dw} = \frac{CF_{dw}}{DWP}$ $CFP_{WW} = \frac{CF_{WW}}{TWW}$ $CFP_{Reclaimed} = \frac{CF_{Reclaimed}}{V_{Reclaimed}}$	kg CO _{2eq} m ⁻³
Waste	8 Water-related materials' Recovery (WR)	By-product material or waste that is recovered and is suitable for its reuse after a treatment process or activity to enhance other activities within the site of interest and the organization scope.	$WR = \frac{W_{i,re}}{W_{i,in}} \times 100$	%
	9 Fertilizer Production Avoided (FPA)	Nutrient recovered used as a fertilizer in relation to the total nutrient used as fertilizer.	$FPA = \frac{N_{i,re}}{N_{i,tot}} \times 100$	%

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs. (Continued)

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement	Unit	
Energy	10 Energy Consumption (E_{eff})	Ratio of the energy consumption for a treatment process or activity.	$E_{eff\ dw} = \frac{E_{dw}}{DWP}$ $E_{eff\ ww} = \frac{E_{ww}}{TWW}$ $E_{eff\ digest} = \frac{E_{digest}}{W_{treated}}$ $E_{eff\ Reclaimed} = \frac{E_{Reclaimed}}{W_{treated}}$	E_{dw} (kWh year ⁻¹): total energy used in the drinking water system (all processes); E_{ww} (kWh year ⁻¹): total energy used in the wastewater system (all processes); DWP (m ³ year ⁻¹): annual drinking water production; used for drinking water systems; TWW (m ³ year ⁻¹): volume of wastewater treated; used for wastewater systems; E_{digest} : total energy consumption in digestion/codigestion (kWh year ⁻¹); $W_{treated}$: total sludge treated (kWh year ⁻¹); $E_{Reclaimed}$: total energy consumption in the process of reclaimed water production (kWh year ⁻¹).	kWh m ⁻³ // kWh tn ⁻¹
	11 Energy Production (EP)	Energy produced from a treatment process (e.g. water/wastewater treatment, codigestion) in relation to the total energy consumption.	$EP = \frac{E_{re}}{E_W} \times 100$	E_{re} (kWh year ⁻¹): energy produced; E_W (kWh year ⁻¹): total energy consumption from a treatment process.	%
Economy and business	12 Circular economy business Models in practice (BM_{CE})	New and modified business models related to circular economy in the water-energy-resources nexus that have already been put into practice related to the new and existing models.	$BM_{CE} = \frac{BM_c}{BM_{tot}} \times 100$	BM_c (No): number of new and modified circular economy business models put into practice; BM_{tot} (No): number of total business models (new and existing). During a period of time.	%
	13 Resource Recovery Revenues (RRR)	Potential revenues that are obtained due to by-products recovered from water or wastewater treatment process.	$RRR = \frac{R_{BP}}{R_{tot}} \times 100$	R_{BP} (€ year ⁻¹): yearly revenue generated from by-products recovery; R_{tot} (€ year ⁻¹): yearly total revenue generated within the organization.	%
Green jobs	14 Green Jobs (GJ)	New jobs created in a circular economy activity over the total amount of jobs.	$GJ = \frac{N_{GJ}}{N_j} \times 100$	NGJ (No year ⁻¹): number of green jobs; NJ (No year ⁻¹): total number of jobs (jobs: created, converted and maintained).	%

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs. (Continued)

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement		Unit	
Social	15	Social Acceptance	Social acceptance refers to the level of approval, recognition, and endorsement that a certain community gives to water-smart solutions, and/or the intentions and likelihood of a community to use and trust in these solutions.	Analysis of stakeholders' attitudes towards the acceptance of water smart solutions carried out in D5.4 (WP5) based on observation at CoP meetings and focus groups.	3 positions of the stakeholders towards circular solutions: 1. Resistant; 2. Neutral; 3. Supportive.	Acceptance score (1-3)
	16	Stakeholder Engagement	Stakeholder engagement is the active participation of local agents and community groups in the decision processes and interventions that affect them.	Accounting of workshop attendees through the collected records/minutes (sex-segregated).	Number of people attending collaborative sessions organised in the different LLs (with gender dimension): 1. Gender imbalance; 2. Gender balance (60% - 40%).	Absolute value & gender dimension
				Accounting of organised and planned events involving stakeholders.	Number of collaborative activities carried out in the project (CoPs, focus groups, etc.).	Absolute value
				Questionnaires carried out in each collaborative/informative session.	"5 positions on the level of stakeholder engagement on the circular solutions' implementation: 1. Inform (1 - 1,5): one-way communication; 2. Consult (1,6 - 2,5): gather opinions; 3. Involve (2,6 - 3,5): mutual learning; 4. Collaborate (3,6 - 4,5): mutual learning and involvement on decision making; 5. Empower (4,6 - 5): stakeholders encouraged to take actions.	Engagement scale (1-5)

Table A1. List of the updated circular economy indicators to be assessed in the Living Labs. (Continued)

Category	Indicator name	Description	Equation / Social measurement		Unit	
Social	17	Awareness and increased understanding	The process to inform and educate people on water challenges and efficient use of natural resources with the intention of influencing their attitudes.	Questionnaires carried out in each collaborative/informative session.	5 positions on the level of awareness and understanding of the water challenge and the circular solutions: 1. Dissociated (1 - 1,5); 2. Unaware (1,6 - 2,5); 3. Curious (2,6 - 3,5); 4. Aware (3,6 - 4,5); 5. Full understanding (4,6 - 5).	Awareness scale (1-5)
	18	Governance compliance	The compliance of implemented solutions in the LL with the 12 OECD principles of Water Governance based on the key dimensions (Effectiveness, Efficiency, Trust and Engagement).	Self-assessment of the OECD principles carried out in WP5 (D5.5).	3 possible scenarios on territorial governance towards circular solutions: 1. Stopper; 2. Neutral; 3. Promoter/enabler.	Governance soundness (1-3)

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